

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable 2.2

Critical ChangeLab PAR Cycle 3

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, Report Critical ChangeLab PAR Cycle 3, presents the activities of Work Package 2 (WP2) during the second cycle of Critical ChangeLab implementation across 19 European locations. WP2 is dedicated to applying the Critical ChangeLab Framework and Process, first developed in WPI, and translating it into practice through participatory and locally responsive approaches. The deliverable reflects the project's emphasis on fostering democratic competencies in diverse contexts while ensuring adaptability to partner needs.

The document outlines preparatory efforts to equip partners, including facilitation support and guidance for designing flexible lab activities. It details the implementation of labs during this cycle, showing both the adaptability of the methodology and the challenges of sustaining youth engagement, balancing structured guidance with local experimentation, and achieving inclusivity.

A central outcome of WP2 has been the further development of a Community of Practice (CoP), which provides a platform for peer learning and exchange. Through the CoP, partners share experiences, identify common challenges, and experiment with creative and participatory tools. These approaches proved particularly effective in engaging young people, especially when activities addressed locally relevant issues and incorporated hands-on methods.

The deliverable also aligns with WP3 (Evaluate) by providing documentation and partner reflections that contribute to the evidence base for assessing outcomes. While full analysis is beyond the scope of this report, the material gathered here supports systematic evaluation.

Key insights from this cycle highlight the importance of iterative reflection, context-sensitive approaches, and the CoP as a mechanism for collective learning. These lessons will inform the Critical ChangeLab Educators Handbook, ensuring that methodologies are shared with formal and non-formal educators. This handbook will contribute to the sustainability of the project, with the aim of continuing to strengthen democratic participation across Europe.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Glossary	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1 Scope	9
2. Process.....	10
2.1 Community of Practice	10
2.2 PAR Cycle 3 Planning Workshops.....	10
2.3 PAR Cycle 3 Planning	11
2.4 Key Performance Indicators	11
3. PAR Cycle 3 Critical ChangeLabs	13
3.1 Trinity College Dublin (Ireland)	16
3.2 University of Oulu (Finland).....	38
3.3 European Alternatives (France).....	48
3.4 LATRA (Greece).....	59
3.5 Institute for Social Research (Croatia)	65
3.6 Ars Electronica (Austria)	82
3.7 Kersnikova (Slovenia).....	93
3.8 Waag Futurelab (Netherlands).....	98
3.9 University of Barcelona (Spain).....	109
3.10 Tactical Tech (Germany, Labs in multiple countries).....	119
4. Twinning Programme	129
5. Key Learnings from PAR Cycle 3.....	147
PAR Cycle 3 Implementation.....	147
Twinning Programme.....	148
6. Conclusion	150

List of Tables

Table 1 - Glossary of terms.....	7
Table 2 - Cumulative KPIs across labs	12
Table 3 - Overview of PAR Cycle 3 labs.....	14
Table 4 - Methods used during the Coláiste Bríde lab.....	20
Table 5 - Methods used during the Design Your Future Fingal lab	25
Table 6 - Methods used during the Design Your Future City lab	30
Table 7 - Methods used during the Treoraigh do Thodhchaí lab.....	34
Table 8 - Trinity College Dublin's KPIs.....	37
Table 9 - Methods used during the AI Ambassadors lab	40
Table 10 - Methods used during the Auta Lasta lab.....	46
Table 11 - University of Oulu's KPIs	47
Table 16 - Methods used during the Mytiline & Kalloni Elementary Schools.....	62
Table 17 - LATRA's KPIs.....	64
Table 18 - Methods used during the Dora Pejačević lab	68
Table 19 - Methods used during the Marija Jambrisak lab.....	74
Table 20 - Methods used during the Novi Zagreb lab.....	78
Table 21 - Institute for Social Research's KPIs	81
Table 22 - Methods used during Europaschule Linz lab.....	84
Table 23 - Methods used during the Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner lab.....	87
Table 24 - Methods used during the Verein SAUM AusbildungsFit Arbeitsraum lab	90
Table 25 - Ars Electronica's KPIs	92
Table 26 - Methods used during Skupna točka – Medgeneracijski center lab.....	95
Table 27 - Kersnikova's KPIs.....	97
Table 28 - Methods used during Don Bosco lab	102
Table 29 - Methods used during Damstede Lyceum lab.....	105
Table 30 - Waag Futurelab's KPIs.....	108
Table 31 - Methods used during the Pineda lab.....	112
Table 32 - Methods used during the TrinitatNova lab.....	115
Table 33 - University of Barcelona's KPIs	118
Table 34 - Overview of Tactical Tech's external labs	121
Table 35 - Tactical Tech's KPIs.....	128

Glossary

Table 1 - Glossary of terms

Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic culture through creative and narrative practices
CCLAB	Critical ChangeLab
CoP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PAR Cycle	Participatory Action Research Cycle
T	Task

1. Introduction

Critical ChangeLab is a collaborative project that brings together young people, educators, civic organisations, and local stakeholders to critically engage with democracy through Participatory Action Research (PAR). It creates inclusive spaces where participants explore democratic processes, co-create knowledge, and test approaches for strengthening civic engagement. The project is grounded in the belief that meaningful participation requires not only theoretical understanding but also active experimentation and reflection.

Work Package 2 (WP2) supports partners in implementing Critical ChangeLabs (CCLABs) across 19 locations in Europe. Building on the framework developed in WP1 (Map & Design), WP2 provides facilitation guidance and opportunities for peer learning. It is closely aligned with WP3 (Evaluate), which draws on partner documentation and reflections to assess outcomes and guide improvements. Together, these work packages ensure an iterative cycle of design, implementation, and refinement.

This deliverable reports on the third PAR cycle (January 2025 through July 2025). It describes partner preparation, the continuation of the Community of Practice (CoP), and the implementation of Critical ChangeLabs in diverse contexts. Insights show the importance of grounding activities in locally relevant issues and using creative, hands-on methods to engage young people in democratic practice. The deliverable also highlights challenges such as sustaining youth participation and balancing structured guidance with local adaptation. The structure of the document is as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the deliverable.

Chapter 2 describes the continuation of the Community of Practice and the preparatory work undertaken with partners for Critical ChangeLab implementation.

Chapter 3 presents narrative accounts of each partner's ChangeLab, outlining activities, reflections, and key performance indicators.

Chapter 4 focuses on the Twinning Programme, describing how it was designed and implemented to foster collaboration between partners, facilitate knowledge exchange, and strengthen cross-contextual learning.

Chapter 5 synthesises learnings from this cycle, including insights into facilitation, youth engagement, and partner collaboration.

Chapter 6 concludes with a discussion of the broader implications of PAR Cycle 3 and outlines how these implications inform the development of the Critical ChangeLab Educators Handbook.

1.1 Scope

This deliverable covers the results of the efforts of PAR Cycle partners and tasks related to their Critical ChangeLabs during PAR Cycle 3. This document details the process of setting up the Critical ChangeLabs, provides a narrative summary of each Critical ChangeLab, and reflects at a high-level on key learnings related to the Critical ChangeLabs and execution of the Community of Practice.

This deliverable is not intended to provide detailed analysis on each Critical ChangeLab, nor a cumulative analysis of the ChangeLabs. This analysis will be detailed in Deliverable 3.1 (Critical ChangeLab Process and Recommendations for Practice). D2.2 and D3.1 will serve as complimentary deliverables - one providing a narrative picture of the labs and their efforts, the other delving into analysis and key insights on implementing the labs overall.

2. Process

2.1 Community of Practice

Building on the Community of Practice (CoP) established in PAR Cycle 2, partners reconvened in PAR Cycle 3 to sustain and expand collaborative exchange. The CoP connects partners implementing and facilitating the labs. It functions as a shared space for mutual support, critical reflection, and the exchange of insights that directly inform lab design and delivery.

Led by Waag Futurelab (WP2, Task 2.1), the CoP's structure was refined during PAR Cycle 3. The group's approach is flexible and tool-light, encouraging active participation, minimising barriers, and adapting to partners' needs. With Waag's coordination, the content and direction are co-shaped by partners, ensuring relevance and shared ownership.

Across both PAR Cycles 2 and 3, the CoP supported the use of the Critical ChangeLab Framework, monitored lab implementation, and facilitated formative evaluation. Activities include:

- **Live Meetings** (three over the two cycles) to align plans, share progress, and reflect on outcomes.
- **Bi-weekly Partner Calls** for regular updates, peer learning, and topical discussions.
- **Online Collaboration** via a shared Miro board for tracking progress, surfacing challenges, and coordinating input.

The CoP also serves as a decision-making forum and links partner practice with youth-facing activities. Its learnings will inform key project outputs such as the MOOC (Deliverable 4.3) and Educator's Handbook (Deliverable 2.3), helping to ensure practices outlast the project.

2.2 PAR Cycle 3 Planning Workshops

To prepare for PAR Cycle 3 implementation, Waag led two online workshops. These sessions built on insights from PAR Cycle 2, aiming to refine partners' plans through collaborative feedback.

Session 1 focused on defining the foundations of each plan, addressing core questions (what, why, how,, and links to the CCL literacies). Partners worked in breakout groups, then rotated for peer feedback. Key takeaways included the need for actionable strategies around imagining alternative futures.

Session 2 centred on refining plans into actionable roadmaps, identifying knowledge gaps, and clarifying logistical needs. Partners shared revised approaches, informed by group discussion, and identified areas needing further research or collaboration.

2.3 PAR Cycle 3 Planning

Planning drew directly from the online sessions. Partners completed a planning template covering stakeholders, target groups, outcomes, activities, and risks, with WP2 providing feedback to strengthen each plan. While flexible, these plans served as guiding frameworks and were shared in bi-weekly CoP calls for peer review and inspiration.

Adjustments from PAR Cycle 2 included:

- Clearer learning objectives (with WP3 input) to balance structure and openness.
- Greater flexibility in non-formal settings, reducing institutional barriers and supporting participant agency.
- Stronger participatory research elements, enabling youth to frame questions, collect data, and co-produce knowledge.

These refinements strengthened the participatory ethos of the Critical ChangeLab model and aligned it more closely with its democratic aims.

2.4 Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were also established to ensure that the target number of students, educators, and organisations were met. These KPIs were tracked via a spreadsheet on SharePoint. Individual KPIs per partner can be found in chapter 2; cumulative KPIs for PAR Cycle 3 are listed below. The number of educator KPIs was not met for this PAR Cycle; across the three PAR Cycles, 292 educators were engaged of the targeted 310. Several reasons emerged as to why

engaging the targeted number of educators was lower. These include that some labs were fully partner-led, particularly in non-formal context, and that representatives from non-formal organisations were considered facilitators as opposed to educators; in addition, timing conflicts were present in formal education settings, particularly with curriculum demands, school calendars, and the pressures of end-of-year exams and reporting.

Table 2 - Cumulative KPIs across labs

	KPI Target	Actuals
Participants in PAR cycle	400	698
Educators	130	103
Number of Civil Society Organisations	15	19

3. PAR Cycle 3 Critical ChangeLabs

This chapter provides narrative descriptions of each partner's Critical ChangeLab facilitated during PAR Cycle 3. Some partners conducted multiple labs to reach their targeted number of students and educators. Each partner report, apart from Tactical Tech, includes a summary of activities and their alignment with the Critical ChangeLab phases, as well as impact, key learnings, and KPIs. The Critical ChangeLab Process and its phases (outlined in D1.4) are supported by the Critical ChangeLab Framework. Tactical Tech's report differs in that they coordinated eight external labs. A key distinction is that in the other partners' labs, researchers were present to take notes, resulting in robust observation and data collection. Tactical Tech's external labs did not include embedded researchers but aimed to extend reach and test feasibility in diverse contexts.

Since gender dynamics shaped both participation and themes across several labs, it is important to note these patterns before moving into the narrative descriptions of each partner's Critical ChangeLab. During PAR Cycle 3, gender diversity appeared in both explicit and implicit ways, with participation varying by setting; some labs were intentionally or structurally single-gender, such as Trinity College Dublin's work with girls at Coláiste Bríde and the Croatian dormitory labs with all-female groups, while most other labs included mixed groups but with a stronger representation of girls. Several labs addressed gender directly, such as European Alternatives in Palermo, where middle-school students focused on unpacking gender stereotypes through games, discussions, and creative films, and the Croatian dormitory labs, where girls focused on mental health, food waste, and drug addiction. Overall, young women were particularly well represented across formal and informal labs, showing both the opportunities for their engagement in democratic reflection and the importance of fostering balanced participation. It is also critical to note that gender is not non-binary, and that all youth participating in labs did not offer up their gender orientation.

The chart below provides an overview of all labs conducted during PAR Cycle 3.

Table 3 - Overview of PAR Cycle 3 labs¹

Partner	Lab	Location	No. of Sessions	Topic
Trinity College Dublin	Coláiste Bríde	Dublin, Ireland	10	Social injustice and future visions of the community
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future Fingal	Dublin, Ireland	5	Imagining the future of their area
Trinity College Dublin	Design Your Future City	Dublin, Ireland	5	Imagining the future of their area
Trinity College Dublin	Treoraigh do Thodhchaí	Galway, Ireland	5	Imagining the future of their area
University of Oulu	AI Ambassadors	Oulu, Finland	10	AI in decision making
University of Oulu	Auta Lasta	Oulu, Finland	1	Making activist jewellery
European Alternatives	Palermo	Palermo, Italy	2	Gender stereotypes
European Alternatives	Pierefitte	Pierefitte, France	5	Artificial intelligence
European Alternatives	Lycée Michel Ange	Villeneuve, France	3	Artificial intelligence
LATRA	Mytilene & Kalloni Elementary Schools	Lesvos, Greece	13	Justice and inclusion
Institute for Social Research	Dora Pejačević	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Food waste

¹ The external labs coordinated by Tactical Tech are not included in this table. A table of the external labs is located in the Tactical Tech section.

Institute for Social Research	Marija Jambrisak	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Mental health (self-image)
Institute for Social Research	Novi Zagreb	Zagreb, Croatia	7	Drug use and addiction among students
Ars Electronica	Europaschule Linz	Linz, Austria	4	Conflict resolution strategies in the classroom
Ars Electronica	Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner	Traun, Austria	2	Envisioning futures
Ars Electronica	Verein Saum	Perg/Linz, Austria	4	The future of work
Kersnikova	DemoBot	Ljubljana, Slovenia	8	Exploring the role of technology in democracy
Wag Futurelab	Don Bosco	Volendam, Netherlands	4	Disinformation and democracy
Wag Futurelab	Damstede Lyceum	Amsterdam Noord, Netherlands	3	Disinformation and democracy
University of Barcelona	Pineda	Barcelona, Spain	6	Democracy and digital technologies
University of Barcelona	TrinitatNova	Barcelona, Spain	10	Injustice in the school context

3.1 Trinity College Dublin (Ireland)

Trinity College Dublin (TCD) – represented by the School of Education – conducted four CCLABs during PAR Cycle 3 – one with Coláiste Bríde (an all-girls secondary school) and three in partnership with the Academy of the Near Future (a non-formal education programme of the CONNECT Research Centre) on their programmes ‘Design Your Future Fingal’ (Fingal, Co. Dublin), ‘Design Your Future City’ (Dublin city) and ‘Treoraigh do Thodhchaí’ (Connemara, Galway).

3.1.1 Coláiste Bríde

Geographical location	Clondalkin, a suburb of Dublin city. Traditionally an 16area of socio-economic disadvantage
Demographic characteristics of participants	Females (all-girls school), aged approx. 15-16. Mixed ethnicities, Clondalkin is a very diverse area.
Number of participants	Ranging from 20-24 (changed each session)
Number of sessions	10
Topic	Social injustice and future visions of the community

This lab was a partnership between TCD and a local secondary school and their Transition Year Sustainability module. It took place in a formal educational setting in the suburbs of Dublin. The lab took place over a number of months on a weekly basis for the most part – due to school holidays and public holidays, there were sometimes gaps between the workshops. The students, aged 15-16, were all in Transition Year in school (a bridge year between the exam cycles where students engage in personal, social, and academic growth) and were all girls.

The workshops were broadly based around exploring the theme of social injustice in their local area, and through the action of [creating a map of their research and their imaginings of the future](#) they engaged more with their local area and reflected on their attitudes towards it. Participants in the focus group noted that the lab gave them "a way to look at, well, what is wrong with our local area that we might not really looked at or paid attention to beforehand" and highlighted "where we can improve". They felt the programme showed them "how much is missing" in the area.

A distinct difference between this lab and TCD's PAR Cycles 1 and 2 was the emphasis on students undertaking their own research on some of the challenges and themes they identified in their area and interpreting the results, as well as the time given to imagining the future of the area. Students learned research methods, such as interviewing, surveying, and photovoice. They then worked in groups in their local area to apply these methods to gather data on their assigned theme, for example, exploring spaces for youth surveyed spaces in their area and interviewed locals using the space. Another group focussed on local amenities surveyed how many people used particular services in a specific time period. A considerable amount of time was taken to introduce the students to research methods, and to support them to familiarise themselves with doing their own inquiry. However, this was an essential element of the participatory action research cycle, and the students expressed engagement and ownership of the project as a result of their involvement as researchers.

By engaging youth in activities such as participatory mapping, it was evident that they value democracy and the rights that democracy affords them (like autonomy and freedom of speech). They were keenly aware of issues related to the theme (social justice) and could speak about rights and inequality. After the programme their teacher reflected that "I think they've learned a lot about the world from - you know, well, their world, I suppose, and their cultural context. I think they're more clued into that now, or at least... You know, they've been able to put language to what they perhaps already know, and perhaps able to look at things in a different way."

However, in terms of participating in their local community or taking actions, there seemed to be a lack of awareness in how to do these things. They observed that the school does these things very well and provides opportunities. Yet the school is not viewed as a place where they can practice democracy, and they don't seem to practice it in their community or at least be aware of when they can.

Figure 1 - Participants gathering data

Key activities:

- *Icebreakers*: Students defined terms like equality, citizenship, and democracy using examples from their community. Many students struggled with this activity, as there was not clear scaffolding, the language was not age-appropriate, and students lacked the context for these ideas on the first day of the programme. This was a big learning point for the team, who developed more scaffolded and creative methods going forward.
- *Independent research*: Students identified and mapped inclusive and exclusive spaces in their schools, making it easier to later identify spaces for improvement in the wider community. Reflecting on positive memories and times they felt frustrated; students connected their personal feelings to specific places. They later brought these research methods to the wider community.

Figure 2 - The worst city for young people to live in, as designed by participants

- *Interviewing a community elder:* Students asked a long-serving teacher in the school about their town's history, gaining a sense of how she had participated in changemaking during her time in the school, and a better understanding of what kinds of challenges are still unresolved. They also got a sense of how life as a young person has changed over the past 50 years.
- *Pitching their ideas:* The experience involved presenting their research and pitching their imagined futures to an invited audience that consisted of senior school leadership, staff of the local authority (county council and library), and a guest university professor who had not previously been part of the programme. This activity was an important one for participants, particularly the experience of adults listening and giving feedback. As a youth said, it "just remind[ed] us that we really do have that voice sometimes". It should be noted though that while this activity was described by students as being important and transformative, there was still a distinct lack of hope for whether this activity would drive any real change.

Figure 3 - Participants mapping their data and their imagined futures

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 4 - Methods used during the Coláiste Bríde lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreakers	Participants engage in simple physical and social exercises to promote group cohesion and energise the session.
Onboard	Competency determination	Students discuss and reflect on CCLAB competencies to identify which ones they believe will guide their upcoming work.
Question	Imagination exercise - Community	A guided visualisation prompts students to reflect on their local community and their experiences in familiar spaces.
Question	Break it before you make it	Students design the worst possible future city to critically reflect on undesirable outcomes and identify themes for further exploration.

Analyse	Mapping – Practicing Research Methods	Groups use different research methods to map areas in their school, collecting data through surveys, sketches, and ethnographic notes.
Analyse	Question Formulation Technique	A high-energy brainstorming session where students generate and refine questions on pre-identified themes for community research.
Analyse	Interview with community elder	Using collaboratively generated questions, students interview a teacher about her experiences in the local area.
Reflecting	Reflection	Students share findings from mapping exercises and discuss social justice themes related to space and community inclusion.
Analyse	Student survey of Clondalkin	Students conduct a self-directed survey of their town to gather data and reflect on local issues.
Envision	Blow up Bus Stops	A creative icebreaker where students redesign bus stops to reflect their vision for improved community spaces.
Analyse	Analysing Data	Students analyse previously gathered data, identify patterns, and discuss opportunities for reimagining community spaces.
Envision	Postcards from the Future	Participants create illustrated postcards imagining future improvements to their local area.
Analyse	Evidence Gathering & Synthesis	Students finalise their evidence collection by selecting key places and information to demonstrate local change over time.
Envision	Finalising Reimagined / Imagined places	Students complete detailed designs for reimagined community spaces, including drawings and labels.
Act	Presentation Preparation	Groups organise their data and designs into presentations, practicing delivery and receiving facilitator feedback.
Act	Presentations	Students present their maps and reimagined places to peers and guests, engaging in discussion on their research and findings.

3.1.2 Design Your Future Fingal

Geographical location	Balbriggan, Co. Dublin, Ireland
Demographic characteristics of participants	4M, 12F. All aged 15-16 years old. All participants living in Fingal (a region in north Dublin that encompasses some of the northern suburbs of the city and towns and villages in the countryside of north Dublin). All in Transition Year of school (aged 15-16)
Number of participants	16
Number of sessions	5
Topic	The overall topic was imagining the future of their local area with a focus on technology, sustainability and community.

TCD partnered with the Academy of the Near Future (a non-formal learning programme of the *CONNECT Research Centre for Future Networks and Communications*), to implement three Critical ChangeLab/Design Your Future labs for young people aged 15-16 in this cycle. Fingal is a suburban/rural region of north county Dublin, and in the Design Your Future Fingal lab, youth from this area explored issues related to sustainability and technology, reimagined the futures of their area, and created prototypes of smart solutions for their communities.

Figure 4 - Students of the 'Design Your Future Fingal' programme analyse historical maps of the area to explore the history of how their area has developed

TCD made some adjustments in this cycle based on our learnings from PAR Cycle 2. Namely, a session on the historical development of the area was brought forward to earlier in the week and a session on imagining speculative futures was moved to later, better aligning with the 'analyse' and 'envision' phases of the Critical ChangeLab model. TCD also focused more on the zine prompts, better aligning them with the phases of the model rather than specific activities students did that day, encouraging reflection on the *why* rather than the *how* of their learning.

Students did a series of workshops with invited speakers and guests, exploring challenges that the area faces and initiatives and solutions being implemented by Fingal County Council and partners. These changes were important, and the facilitators and researchers felt that they made sense within the context of the Critical ChangeLab and contributed positively to the week. However, due to difficulties and tensions within the group there were concerns about the depth of critical analysis students engaged in and the level of transformative agency that was fostered on an individual level.

Figure 5 – Students of the ‘Design Your Future Fingal’ programme explore how the local authorities have been using ‘digital twinning’ and VR to address challenges in the local area

Key Activities

- *“Break It Before You Make It”*: Students realized that even their worst-case future cities reflected real fears. By engaging in intentionally “bad” design, students developed clearer insight into what *good* design should look like. They could articulate what they wanted “the future” to look like but struggled to use these hopes to influence decision-making.
- *Ethics Workshop*: Most students felt that young people have little influence on climate change, despite feeling that they care deeply about the issue. They felt disconnected from decision-making, displaying a gap in their viewpoints between perceived and actual agency.
- *Problem Generation/Prototyping*: Underlying tensions between students and facilitators made it challenging for students to categorize the different issues they wanted to focus on and start generating ideas. Prototyping was delayed for this reason, so students experienced the realistic challenges that come with working under time pressure.

Table 5 details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 5 - Methods used during the Design Your Future Fingal lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreaker – Introduce Your Table	Participants introduced each other, shared hopes and fears, created a group manifesto, and engaged in a line-up game to build trust and rapport.
Question	Break It Before You Make It	In groups, students designed the worst possible city of the future to critically reflect on values and aspirations for sustainable urban design.
Analyse	Our Evolving Area	Students analysed historical maps and engaged in group discussion to explore how their area has evolved over time under social and economic influences.
Analyse	Digital Twin Workshop	A lecture introduced digital twins and local initiatives, followed by hands-on VR exploration and design tasks for applying the concept to their community.
Reflect	Zine making	Students reflected on their day's experiences by creating personal zines with drawings and collages responding to a provided prompt.
Analyse	Biodiversity Workshop	A local biodiversity officer gave a talk, and students collaboratively designed green buildings and parks that integrate biodiversity principles.
Analyse	Micro:bit Coding	Students learned coding and prototyping by designing interactive micro:bit 'pets' that respond to environmental stimuli.
Analyse	Ethics Workshop	An interactive session featuring drawing exercises and walking debates encouraged students to critically reflect on ethical dimensions of sustainability and technology.
Envision	Speculative Design	Groups imagined life on new planets by designing colonies that addressed biological, security, and social needs using creative materials.
Analyse	Circular Economy Workshop	After a presentation, students worked in teams to design circular economy solutions for their local council and shared them with the group.

Analyse	Active Travel Workshop	Students mapped their neighbourhoods, identified barriers to active travel, and discussed solutions for encouraging sustainable transportation.
Analyse	Problem Definition and Idea Generation	Participants reviewed previous findings, organised issues into themes, and collaboratively defined problems and brainstormed solutions.
Analyse	Practising Pitching: Crap Ideas	Students created intentionally bad ideas and pitched them, developing communication and critical reflection skills in a playful format.
Act	Prototyping	Teams developed physical prototypes of their solutions and refined their concepts in preparation for final presentations.
Act	Presentations	Students pitched their prototypes to a panel of judges, answered questions, and received constructive feedback.

3.1.3 Design Your Future City

Geographical location	Dublin City (urban)
Demographic characteristics of participants	12 female, 7 male
Number of participants	19
Number of sessions	5
Topic	The overall topic was imagining the future of their local area with a focus on technology, sustainability and community.

TCD partnered with the Academy of the Near Future to implement three Critical ChangeLab/Design Your Future City labs for young people aged 15-16. In this lab youth from Dublin city explored issues related to sustainability and technology, reimagined the futures of their areas, and created prototypes of smart solutions for their communities.

Figure 6 – Students at Trinity College Dublin analysing historical maps of the city

TCD made further adjustments to the lab based on learnings from PAR Cycle 2 and from the Design Your Future Fingal lab. The main change we focused on for this week was reinstating an experienced facilitator and focusing on envisioning and imagining futures. The reason for this focus on envisioning and imagining futures was because we had noted that in previous labs that the participants would imagine futures, but that there was often a disconnect between the futures they imagined and the action they wanted to take on for their locality. It was observed that this week was the strongest in imagining futures (of the DYFC labs that we collaborated on) – researchers believe this is due to tweaking the futures-imagining exercise from ‘speculative futures’ (on other planets) to thinking about futures of Dublin before engaging in designing solutions for the future – futures are imagined, then solutions are created.

Overall, when discussing the programme participants felt that it changed how they think about their ability to make a difference. Seeing examples of other teenagers making a difference, like the "street light thing," (a project which caught the interest of one of the members of Dublin City Council) was inspiring to them. A significant realisation for some was that "your voice matters, and like, people will listen to you if you have something to say". They felt that their ideas were valued and that

"nothing is wrong" with what they proposed, as "everything is taken into consideration".

Key Activities

- *'Speculative' Futures*: This activity, which had previously been moved from earlier in the week to the Thursday (just before participants create prototypes of solutions) was further revised to focus not on 'speculative' futures on far-away planets, but focused on the city of Dublin. An additional layer, inspired by the digital twinning programme, encouraged students to create postcards from the future, in which they wrote headlines and drew pictures of the role they have played in creating these futures. This was a huge success in this cycle, with students reflecting more on their agency in creating these futures than ever before.

Figure 7 - Postcards from the future, showing how participants imagine themselves to have been involved in creating that future

- *Local Challenges Research Activity*: A member of Dublin City Council presented a report to young people on challenges faced by locals living in the city. Students were given headings and asked to analyse the data related to

their areas. While there were some challenges in students interpreting the data, this is the first time students have been encouraged to interpret actual data and is an important step in Participatory Action Research.

Figure 8 - Students of the Design Your Future City programme gathering data for analysis

- *Idea Generation:* Students demonstrated high levels of creativity, with lots of connections made to personal experiences, previous classroom discussions, and real-world problems. Students engaged in thoughtful debate about what language should be used to describe the challenges they were looking at, and they worked collaboratively to resolve issues.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 6 – Methods used during the Design Your Future City lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreaker – Introduce Yourself	Participants engage in introductory activities to build trust, share expectations, and co-create a group manifesto.
Question	Break It Before You Make It	Students design 'worst possible' future cities in small groups to critically reflect on urban planning and societal priorities.
Analyse	Our Evolving Area	Students analyse historical maps and discuss how Dublin's development has been shaped by social, economic, and environmental factors.
Analyse	Active Travel Workshop	An interactive session where students discuss barriers to active travel and brainstorm inaccessible city designs.
Reflection	Reflection: Zine making	Participants reflect on the day's activities by creating personal zines with drawings or collages.
Envision	Creative Methods – Drama Futuring	Groups use freeze-frame and drama exercises to envision future scenarios about travel, environment, and urban adaptation.
Analyse	Biodiversity Walking Tour & Workshop	A guided tour of Trinity's campus exploring biodiversity, followed by group discussion on environmental issues.
Analyse	Micro:bit Coding Workshop – MicroPets	Students design and code interactive 'MicroPets' using micro:bit devices to explore coding and teamwork.
Envision	Creative Methods – Drama Imagining and Futuring	Students create group body sculptures and role-play futuristic scenarios to explore imaginative thinking.
Analyse	Water Lecture, Sampling and Testing	A lecture and hands-on session where students sample and test water from local sources to learn about environmental science.
Reflect	Stop-Start-Continue	Students provide feedback on the programme by writing suggestions for improvements, continuations, or changes.
Analyse	Ethics workshop – Climate and Sustainability	Participants engage in drawing exercises and a walking debate to reflect on ethics in climate action and sustainability.

Envision	Speculative Futures Imagining	Students envision Dublin in 2050 by creating illustrated postcards depicting future scenarios.
Analyse	Local Challenges Research Activity	Groups analyse local data and reports to create posters highlighting key challenges in their community.
Analyse	Smart City Challenge: Problem Defining & Idea Generation	Students define urban challenges and generate creative solutions in a collaborative, high-energy session.
Analyse	Communication Workshop – Worst Ideas	Participants design and pitch intentionally bad products to explore communication and creative thinking.
Act	Idea Prototyping	Groups develop physical prototypes of their concepts, preparing them for presentation to a judging panel.
Act	Idea Pitching / Presentation Preparations	Teams refine their presentations and pitch prototypes to a panel, receiving feedback and answering questions.
Act	Student Presentations	Final group presentations showcasing projects that integrate research, creativity, and social awareness.

3.1.4 Treoraigh do Thodhchaí

Geographical location	An Spidéal, Conamara, Galway, Ireland
Demographic characteristics of participants	All were aged 15-17, all white Irish. This was conducted in a primarily Irish-language speaking area and was conducted all through the medium of Irish.
Number of participants	14 – 20
Number of sessions	5 (5 days – multiple sessions on each day)
Topic	The overall topic was imagining the future of their area, with a focus on technology, sustainability and the Irish language.

As part of TCD’s collaboration with the Academy of the Near Future, one of the labs was delivered in the Irish language, in a rural coastal area in the west of Ireland (An Spidéal, Conamara). An additional partner, Gael Linn was involved in the delivery of this lab. Gael Linn is an organisation dedicated to promoting the Irish language through educational and cultural activities. A key ambition for all partners was that

the same kind of future-oriented STEAM learning that the Academy of the Near Future provided in Dublin through the English language would be available through the Irish language for Irish-speaking youth. Many of the participants of this lab have done all of their education to date in Irish, and many speak Irish in their homes as their first language. However, others who attended do not live in a Gaeltacht (primarily Irish-speaking) area or in Irish-speaking homes, but attend schools where Irish is the medium of education and have a high level of fluency and interest in the language.

Figure 9 – Student researches the significance of the Irish name for the wood anemone: “lus na gaoithe”

The programme name was translated into the Irish language slightly differently as *Treoraigh do Thodcháí* (*Steer your Future*) as it was aimed at young people from across this rural region rather than all from one town or city. A crucial aspect agreed upon by the partner organisations during the planning phases was that *Treoraigh do Thodcháí* was not *about* the Irish language but rather conducted through it.

Futures thinking activities would naturally involve futures in which Irish language would be the spoken language – so it should never become a programme about “saving” the Irish language but rather normalising learning about sustainability, technology and futures thinking in the same language that these students do their everyday education, not requiring them to switch to English to learn about and discuss such topics as is often the case outside of school. While artistic and historical approaches had been used in other *Design Your Future* labs in this cycle, the partnership with Gael Linn led to an additional focus on cultural heritage and Irish traditional arts. The overall challenge for participants, like in the other *Design Your Future* labs in this PAR Cycle, was to prototype an innovation that would address a sustainability issue for the area, and present ideas to professionals from academia, industry, media and local authorities. Despite the strong focus on community and sustainability in the workshops all through the week, none of the solutions pitched were explicitly aimed at collectively addressing local climate issues and rather focused on tackling problems facing individual young people, such as mental and physical health. One project proposed using technology to support the increased use of the Irish language in everyday life in Ireland.

Figure 10 – Students analysing river water samples to investigate water quality

The table below details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 7 - Methods used during the Treoraigh do Thodhchaí lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreaker – Introduce Yourself	Participants engage in introductory activities to build trust, share expectations, and co-create a group manifesto.
Question	Break It Before You Make It	In small groups, students design 'worst possible' future Gaeltacht areas to critically reflect on rural planning, infrastructures and societal priorities.
Analyse	Our Evolving Area: native woodlands	Students learn about native woodlands and local conservation efforts from an ecologist and a community activist. In a workshop, they reflect on their connections with the land and waters in the area, and design imaginary future spaces for young people in the community woodland that is being developed.
Analyse	Open Street Mapping Workshop	An interactive session where students created a map of the local area in teams using a variety of materials, to investigate how information can be communicated with different media. Students use a digital citizen science tool to map infrastructure in local outdoor area.
Envision	Creative Methods – Drama Imagining and Futuring	Students create group body sculptures and role-play futuristic scenarios to explore imaginative thinking.
Reflection	Zine making	Participants reflect on their learning by creating personal zines with drawings or collages.
Analyse	Biodiversity & Folklore Workshop	Participants explored biodiversity in the local area, documenting and identifying animals and plants, and then investigated and shared folklore stories around those local species.
Analyse	Micro:bit Coding Workshop	Students design and code interactive 'creatures' using micro:bit devices to explore coding, creativity and teamwork.

Analyse & Envision	Citizen Science- Water Sampling and Testing	An outdoor, hands-on session where students sample and test water at the local river to learn about environmental science and citizen science. Participants then returned to the classroom and, using their own instruments, composed a music piece together, reflecting on the 'future of water'.
Act	Music Creation Workshop	Students collected & shared audio samples related to water earlier in the week. This interactive workshop was held immediately after outdoor water sampling activity. Musician facilitator used electronic audio samples and guided students through live improvised music creation using real and makeshift instruments and voices, resulting in a final audio track.
Analyse	Ethics workshop - Climate and Sustainability	Participants engage in drawing exercises and a walking debate to reflect on ethics in climate action and sustainability.
Envision	Speculative Futures Imagining	Students envision the Gaeltacht in 2050 by creating news bulletins depicting future scenarios.
Question	Innovation + Product Design	Students learn from a local company about how an idea is taken from conception to prototype to market and have to sketch out their own design for a real product the company is currently working on for a sports team.
Analyse	Challenge: Problem Defining & Idea Generation	Students define sustainability challenges facing Gaeltacht areas and generate creative solutions in a collaborative, high-energy session.
Act	Idea Prototyping	Groups settle on a challenge to address and develop physical prototypes of their solutions, preparing them for presentation to a judging panel.
Act	Student Presentations	Final group presentations showcasing projects that integrate research, creativity, and social awareness. Prototypes are pitched to a panel, receiving feedback and answering questions

3.1.5 Key Learnings and Impact

Four key learnings emerged across the CCLABs. These include:

1. **Centring the student voice for agency.** Allowing students to shape lesson activities (e.g., wording, topics) and prompting them to explore their own interests fosters deeper engagement and a stronger sense of agency.
2. **The importance of facilitation.** Addressing tensions and incorporating feedback, even when challenging, is crucial. Facilitators must balance curriculum goals with adaptability to student needs and experiences. This can be challenging to implement in certain settings (e.g., a school with strict rules) but can positively impact the lab. Working in formal school settings can make it hard for students to take initiative and feel in control – facilitators should consider the space that they’re in and encourage students to step out of that “comfort zone”, welcoming all student ideas.
3. **Design for relevance and empowerment.** Engagement improves when students connect content to their personal backgrounds and memories. Building from shared experiences and real-life contexts (rather than abstract definitions) helps develop meaningful understanding and action.
4. **The importance of the local.** Students connected better to ideas and concepts when they were linked to their local area, community, and their experiences.

Students reported a deeper understanding of their communities and a stronger connection to local issues after engaging directly with stakeholders and evaluating challenges in their own areas. They valued the focus on local problems over abstract global issues, which made the learning feel more relevant and actionable. Many reflected that assessing what worked and what didn’t in their surroundings helped them see realistic ways to improve their communities.

The lab also supported growth in communication, presentation, and collaboration skills, while the social bonds formed during workshops fostered a sense of inclusion and collective agency. However, the impact on students’ sense of agency was uneven. Some felt empowered by the creative, hands-on approach, while others questioned whether their contributions could lead to lasting change. A few described a “false sense of hope” about influencing civic structures, highlighting the need to manage expectations and provide clearer pathways for impact.

One student reflected on how the experience motivated him to volunteer locally: “Before this, I never felt like the city or the community had anything to do with me –

it all felt out of my control. I didn't think people my age had any real say in what happens. But through this programme, I learned that a lot of decisions are actually shaped by people like us, often behind the scenes. And seeing how much others care – like one of my friends who's really involved in this kind of work – helped me realise how important it is for young people to be part of shaping the community."

This kind of transformation, however, was not universal. Others came away with a clearer sense of the barriers to change and a more tempered view of what young people can achieve without structural support. One student in our labs articulated this in our focus groups

"Yeah, because it's like, very hard to put things into action, especially with how many barriers you'll have to get through – so many barriers and so many people. So, it's just, like, harder to make the world a better place."

3.1.6 Trinity College Dublin's Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between TCD's CCLABs.

Table 8 – Trinity College Dublin's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	80
Participants from underrepresented groups	54
Educators	20
Other stakeholders	8
Researchers-facilitators	4
Number of participants (in final focus group)	70
Number of educators (in final interview)	3
Number of CSOs	1
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	2

3.2 University of Oulu (Finland)

The University of Oulu (Oulu) conducted two labs during PAR Cycle 3 – one titled AI Ambassadors within the University of Oulu and the other with Auta Lasta, a children’s home.

3.2.1 AI Ambassadors

Geographical location	Oulu, Finland
Demographic characteristics of participants	15-17 year olds 20 participants (11 girls, 9 boys) 6 girls and 3 boys from immigrant background
Number of participants	20
Number of sessions	10
Topic	AI in Decision Making

This lab was conducted as part of a two-week summer work programme focused on engaging participants in critical explorations of artificial intelligence (AI) and its role in decision-making. The AI Ambassador programme combined hands-on activities introducing participants to key AI concepts such as Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, language models, and chatbots. The City of Oulu partly funded the youth’s summer work traineeship, with the other half funded through the University. (The city did not fund the lab itself but provided vouchers to the young people who applied summer work as part of their programme to support youth get work experiences.) The programme encouraged young people to experiment with AI tools while fostering critical thinking and ethical awareness. Beyond technical skills, the programme included creative activities (based on designing future scenarios, digital fabrication and making, as well as creating design fictions videos), which were combined with discussion-based and research-oriented activities to support a multifaceted understanding of emerging technologies and their societal implications. Throughout the lab, participants were introduced to various futures through dedicated activities (such as the futures wheel, futures triangle, etc.) that helped them develop a taxonomy of futures.

As part of the lab, participants received media training in collaboration with the [Mannerheim League for Child Welfare](#), the largest non-governmental child welfare organisation in Finland, and communication experts from the Information

Technology and Electrical Engineering (ITEE) Faculty of the University of Oulu, as well as a professional journalist. During the programme, participants developed a group project based on an area of concern regarding the use of AI in decision making of their choice. Throughout the different activities, young people identified, questioned, examined and envisioned alternative AI systems. They presented their futures speculation in the form of design fictions that were disseminated through the AI Ambassador social media, as well as [Nuortennetti](#) (a Finnish online platform maintained by the Mannerheim League for Child Welfare, designed specifically for young people).

Figure 11 - Participants creating decision trees from the data

During the previous lab cycle (PAR 2), participants' feedback indicated that the activities involved extensive writing, which they were already accustomed to through their schoolwork. Additionally, the time allocated for these activities was considered insufficient. In response, this PAR cycle incorporated more hands-on tasks and independent group projects, allowing participants greater autonomy in managing their time and workload across different days. This approach created more flexibility for participants to engage with the projects at their own pace and coordinate their group work independently.

Figure 12 – Participants working on their futures wheel for the selected topic

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 9 – Methods used during the AI Ambassadors lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Ice-breaker: Speed Intros	Pairs of participants interviewed each other and introduced their partners to the whole group, fostering connection and active listening.
Onboard	Group making	Participants mapped their skills and formed diverse groups, encouraging reflection on team dynamics and individual strengths.
Onboard	Competences (co-meaning making, self-evaluating and prioritizing)	Groups discussed and defined key competences, assessed their proficiency, and selected priorities for further development.
Onboard	Shared Code of Conduct	Groups defined guiding principles for collaboration, fostering a respectful and inclusive working environment.

Question	Introduction to ML Algorithms: Fishbowl	Participants explored algorithmic bias via an online simulator, followed by an emotional mapping and structured fishbowl discussion.
Question	Guest lecture: AI in journalist professional practice	A science journalist discussed AI's role in journalism, its opportunities and limitations, followed by a Q&A session. This session was led by a science communication specialist of the University of Oulu ITEE faculty.
Question	Creating content for the AI Ambassadors social media channels	Groups reflected on daily learnings and created social media posts at the end of each session to share insights and trigger public dialogue about AI in decision-making.
Question	Icebreaker: Blobs and Lines	Participants formed groups or lined up based on shared traits, encouraging informal interaction and building community spirit.
Question	Questioning possible futures: Futures archetypes of ML algorithms	Groups brainstormed AI-based apps for love and friendship using futures archetypes and presented their concepts to peers.
Question	Video production training	A youth worker working at MLL introduced online youth engagement tools and guided participants through producing creative content for social media.
Question	Icebreaker: Drawing democracy	Students visualised democracy as a place or object, then revised their drawings imagining AI's influence on democratic decision-making.
Question	Questioning how ML algorithms work: Teachable Machine	Groups built simple ML models, tested for bias, and reflected on the ethical implications of data and algorithms.
Question	Democracy and AI in Decision Making	Groups mapped connections between democratic values and AI systems, discussing tensions and opportunities in a collaborative format.
Question	Selecting a Topic and Photovoice	Participants chose topics related to AI in daily life, created visual stories, and presented them to reflect on societal impacts of AI.

Analyse	Questioning how ML algorithms work: Decision Trees I	Participants manually designed decision trees, peer-reviewed them, and discussed critical issues in algorithmic decision-making.
Analyse	Futures Wheel: Analysing consequences of AI in Decision Making	Groups created futures wheels to explore ripple effects of AI on various aspects of life and society.
Analyse	Ice-Breaker: Guess the secret rule	Participants engaged in a hidden-rule selection activity to reflect on fairness, exclusion, and AI decision-making.
Analyse	Questioning how ML algorithms work: Decision Trees II	Participants collaboratively designed, tested, and refined decision trees, both on paper and via a chatbot. They used peer feedback to improve logic, features, and flow.
Analyse	AI Plausible Futures: Futures Triangle	Participants worked in groups to create and share Futures Triangles, exploring present trends, past barriers, and future aspirations for AI in decision-making. Ask ChatGPT
Envision & examine	Creating Voice of Youth Videos	Participants created short, engaging "Voices of Youth" videos capturing their perspectives and experiences on AI and decision-making, drawing on CCLAB activities and personal reflections for authentic storytelling.
Envision & examine	Envisioning desirable AI futures: Producing Design Fiction for social media I	Participants explored alternative futures through design fiction by envisioning desirable AI futures, brainstorming smart objects, and collaboratively developing storyboards that reflected their values, concerns, and hopes for AI in everyday life.
Envision & examine	Envisioning desirable AI futures: Producing Design Fiction for social media II	Participants created audio-visual stories (design fictions) to express their envisioned AI futures, designing future artifacts and critically reflecting on AI algorithms through collaborative storytelling and detailed storyboarding.
Envision & examine	Maker activity: speculative artifacts' visual identity	Participants designed and created custom canvas bags representing their design fiction ideas, using Inkscape, a vinyl cutter, and a heat press

Envision & examine	Digital Fabrication and making futures artifacts for the design fiction videos	Participants digitalized their envisioned future objects in Inkscape, selected materials, and used laser cutting or 3D printing to fabricate artifacts for their design fiction videos.
Envision & examine	Design Fiction Videos (shooting and editing)	Participants shot and edited their design fiction videos.
Act	Sharing and giving feedback to VoY and Design Fiction Videos	Participants watched each other's videos, exchanging feedback and gaining insight into the issues and approaches their peers explored.
Act	Pecha Kucha preparation	Participants prepared and rehearsed Pecha Kucha presentations to creatively and concisely reflect on their process, experiences, and learnings from the AI Ambassador program.
Act	Final Group presentations	The participants delivered group Pecha Kucha presentations in front of another group of 20 teenagers and audience members (parents, researchers) and screened their videos, followed by a feedback and Q&A session.

3.2.2 Auta Lasta

Geographical location	Oulu, Finland
Demographic characteristics of participants	16-18 years old 4 participants - 3 Girls, 1 Boy Living in a foster home
Number of participants	4
Number of sessions	1
Topic	Making activist jewellery to start conversations about the issues that you are worried about in your everyday lives, or things that you want to celebrate.

This lab was organised as a digital fabrication and making activity designed to engage participants in the creation of tangible artifacts that express their ideas, concerns, and voices. The activity aimed to promote self-expression and

community engagement through creative practices, while also introducing participants to basic design and fabrication tools.

The session started with the participants identifying issues they wanted to raise awareness about or spark discussions on within their communities. Building on these themes, they developed slogans and initial design ideas for activist jewellery or keychains - first sketching them on paper and then refining the designs using computer-based design tools. The session concluded with participants fabricating their designs using a laser cutter and assembling the final pieces.

Figure 13 - Designing the artifact first on paper and later using the inkscape software

One of the challenges encountered during PAR Cycle 1 was participant reluctance to commit to multi-session engagements, especially within non-formal or community-based settings. To address this, the current session was structured as a single two-hour workshop, enabling participants to take part without the burden of extended commitment. This condensed format not only increased participation but also fostered a sense of immediate accomplishment, as each participant left with a personalised, physical artifact that embodied their own voice and ideas.

Figure 14 - Cutting the design using a laser cutter

We ended up doing one-on-one interviews (10-15 mins) with the participants at the end mainly; we chose to do so as each participant had a different issue they wanted to discuss and raise awareness about. In addition, the pace of each participant for this was different. For example, one girl was already done with designing and creating the artifact while some were still thinking about what they wanted to talk about.

Figure 15 - Participants showing the final product after assembling

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 10 - Methods used during the Auta Lasta lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Question-Analyse-Act	Digital Fabrication: Jewellery making	Participants reflected on the issues they care about. They designed 2D images using Inkscape and created jewellery or keychains with laser-cut messages to raise awareness about these issues by combining ideation, digital design, and hands-on assembly.

3.2.3 Key Learnings and Impact

Four key lessons emerged from the CCLABs.

1. Hands-on, creative activities greatly enhance engagement by allowing participants to express themselves through tangible artifacts, which fosters a sense of ownership and pride.
2. Providing flexibility in how participants manage their time and work, especially through group projects, supports deeper collaboration and allows for individual pacing, improving overall outcomes.
3. Introducing digital tools like laser cutters and design software opens new avenues for creative expression and skill development, making technology more accessible and meaningful for children. On the challenging side, time constraints posed limitations, as shorter sessions encouraged participation but restricted opportunities for deeper reflection and group discussion (in Auta Lasta Lab).
4. The importance of creating emotionally safe and supportive environments was clear; when participants felt heard and respected, they were more willing to engage openly and critically.

The labs had a multifaceted impact on participants and the wider community. For participants, it provided an opportunity to express their thoughts and concerns through creative, hands-on activities, moving beyond the traditional classroom approaches they are used to. They gained confidence in using digital fabrication

tools and AI generative tools (for many it was the first experience of using FABLAB, using AI for generating images and creating videos). The physical artifacts they created allowed them to see their ideas take tangible form, reinforcing a sense of ownership and agency. Many participants shared their work with pride, demonstrating increased self-expression and awareness of social issues.

Within the community, the labs fostered a platform for youth voices to be seen and heard, sparking conversations around topics that matter to them. As the participants shared their daily activities as well as the discussions or ideas on social media, this created a ripple effect of awareness and engagement encouraging dialogue beyond the lab and inspiring peers and other community members to take interest in the issues raised by the youth. The shift from passive learning to active engagement helped nurture early forms of civic thinking and accountability, supporting broader goals of inclusion, sustainability, and ethical awareness. The positive reception of the lab also laid the foundation for future community partnerships and youth-led initiatives.

3.2.4 University of Oulu Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between University of Oulu’s CCLABs.

Table 11 – University of Oulu’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	24
Participants from underrepresented groups	18
Educators	4
Other stakeholders	7
Researchers-facilitators	6
Number of participants (in final focus group)	22
Number of educators (in final interview)	0
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	0
Number of non-formal education organizations	3

3.3 European Alternatives (France)

European Alternatives conducted three labs during PAR Cycle 3 – one in Palermo, Italy, with the ETS Association (non-profit organization), as well one with Pierrefitte, and one with Lycée Michel Ange (school), both located in France.

3.3.1 Palermo

Geographical location	Palermo, Italy
Demographic characteristics of participants	Middle school boys and girls, aged 11-13, Italian-speaking, from working-class neighbourhoods
Number of participants	10
Number of sessions	2
Topic	Gender stereotypes, explored through dialogue, reflection, and creative video production

The third PAR cycle in Palermo was conducted with YOLK, an ETS association running after-school activities for young people. The cycle involved 10 middle-school students, who were recruited during a “circle” discussion at their after-school club. Building on previous cycles, this lab aimed to deepen reflection on gender stereotypes while combining it with creative expression through video-making. This marked a shift from PAR Cycle 2, where activities had been more limited to discussion and reflection. The decision to introduce audio-visual production stemmed from two factors: the children’s natural curiosity for technology and storytelling, and the desire to create tangible outputs that could extend the impact beyond the group itself. The sessions began with familiar circle discussions and ice-breaker activities, where participants introduced themselves and reflected on gender roles. Through games, they illustrated and mimed stereotypical and non-stereotypical situations (a mother washing dishes vs. a boy crying and being consoled). These exercises helped participants recognise how stereotypes affect daily life and opened conversations on issues like sexist language, access to sports, and household expectations.

The second part of the cycle shifted to hands-on creative activities. Participants learned basic filming skills, experimented with professional cameras, and worked collaboratively to conduct interviews and stage fictional scenes. Each child contributed according to their inclinations: some preferred directing, others acting,

while others focused on interviewing. This experiential learning allowed them to explore the theme of stereotypes in a more personal and engaging way.

Figure 16 – Youth working on production

The change from discussion-only methods to storytelling and audio-visual creation proved crucial. It gave the young participants ownership of the process, helped maintain attention, and fostered collective responsibility. Importantly, it allowed them to express complex reflections in accessible and creative forms. The cycle concluded with the production of 15 short videos addressing different dimensions of gender stereotypes, balancing fun, critical reflection, and artistic exploration.

Figure 17 – Students working on their videos

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Ice-breaking and discussion circle	Participants introduced themselves in a circle and engaged in a group discussion on gender inequality to build listening and dialogue skills.
Analyse	Game on stereotypes - imaginary	A drawing and miming game encouraged participants to identify and critically reflect on societal stereotypes and roles.
Analyse	Reflecting on stereotypes and how to combat them	Back in a discussion circle, participants shared personal experiences with stereotypes and brainstormed ways to challenge them.

Analyse	Explanation	Introduce basic filming and interviewing techniques, where participants learn to use cameras and conduct interviews.
Envision	Writing board	Group work to script scenarios challenging stereotypes, encouraging imaginative alternatives.
Act	Producing	Collaborative filming and editing of short videos, enabling participants to create outputs that express their reflections.
Reflect	Discussion	Screening of the videos within the group, followed by discussion on insights and learnings.

3.3.2 Pierrefitte

Geographical location	Pierrefitte, France
Demographic characteristics of participants	Young people aged 14-15
Number of participants	22
Number of sessions	5
Topic	Artificial Intelligence

The Pierrefitte lab was structured as a sequence of sessions that combined orientation, critical dialogue, and creative practice. The initial activities focused on onboarding, with the aim of building a shared understanding of the topic and establishing a collaborative atmosphere. Participants were then guided through structured discussions that examined the presence of artificial intelligence in everyday life. These conversations addressed both technical and ethical dimensions with particular attention to issues of privacy, education, and social relationships.

An important adjustment made after the PAR2 cycle was the introduction of a clearer balance between discussion-based activities and hands on creative exercises. This combination proved effective in maintaining motivation and engagement, as it allowed students to alternate between analytical reflection and artistic expression.

Zine making was introduced as the central creative anchor of the lab. Working in small groups, participants produced zines that combined collage, illustration, and text to express their perspectives on AI. This activity provided a concrete outlet for reflection and ensured that contributions extended beyond verbal discussion. In particular, it created opportunities for more reserved participants to engage actively, supporting inclusivity and collective ownership of the outcomes.

The lab was co-designed and facilitated by a partnership involving educators, cultural practitioners and creative technologists. Their collaboration ensured that the sessions integrated pedagogical structure with artistic experimentation and critical inquiry. This interdisciplinary approach enabled participants to engage with AI not only as a technical subject but also as a cultural and social reality that requires multiple perspectives.

The final stage of the lab resulted in the production of a collection of zines that documented and communicated the students' reflections. These outputs functioned both as learning artifacts and as tools for sharing insights with peers, educators, and the wider community. Overall, the lab demonstrated the value of combining participatory discussion with creative practice to deepen critical engagement with emerging technologies.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 2 - Methods used during the Pierrefitte lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreakers and group-building games	Activities to build trust, establish group dynamics, and introduce the theme of AI.
Question	Guided discussions on perceptions of AI in everyday life	Facilitated dialogue exploring how students encounter AI in education, social media, and daily routines.
Analyse	Small group debates and collective brainstorming	Structured debates on risks and opportunities of AI; mapping potential scenarios together.

Envision	Zine-making workshops (collage, drawing, text)	Creative sessions where each participant designed pages imagining possible AI futures.
Act	Presentation of Zines	Students shared their creative work with peers and facilitators, opening space for dialogue and feedback.
Reflect	Group reflection and discussion	Collective review of learnings, key insights, and possible next steps for future engagement.

3.3.3 Lycée Michel Ange

Geographical location	Villeneuve la Garenne, France
Demographic characteristics of participants	Young people between 17-18
Number of participants	18
Number of sessions	3
Topic	Artificial Intelligence

The lab in France was designed as a sequence of participatory sessions combining orientation, critical dialogue and creative production. The programme began with onboarding activities, including icebreakers and framing of AI as a theme to establish trust and introduce the topic. From there participants engaged in structured discussions exploring where AI appears in everyday life, particularly in education, work, and social relationships. Case studies of tools such as ChatGPT or facial recognition were used to spark debate about risks and opportunities, leading to small group discussions that mapped possible scenarios.

A key refinement from PAR Cycle 2 was the programme design itself: greater emphasis was placed on the construction of zines, and more alternation was introduced between analytical and creative activities. This change was made to better adapt the programme to a younger cohort of 14–15-year-olds, who were generally less engaged in school and less used to abstract debate. The zine-making process, which included collage, drawing, and text, proved highly effective in maintaining motivation, offering a concrete and inclusive outlet for participation. Students created zines to exchange with peers in Greece, and later curated them into a collaborative exhibition, which allowed them to present their perspectives to facilitators and one another.

For older participants (17–18 years old), the same thematic focus on AI was pursued but with a different emphasis. Here, discussions took on a more analytical tone, with structured debates on ethical implications and extended reflection on possible utopian and dystopian futures of education. Zine-making was retained as a synthesis exercise enabling students to translate critical insights into creative form. Compared to the younger group in Pierrefitte, older participants were more vocal in discussions and engaged in deeper critical questioning, though the creative activities remained an important complement to dialogue.

Figure 18 – Cutting zines, Villeneuve La Garenne Students

The lab was delivered through collaboration between educators, cultural practitioners, and creative technologists who combined expertise ensuring that pedagogical structure and artistic experimentation were present. The process resulted in both a set of zines as tangible learning outputs and an expanded space for young people to articulate their perspectives on the social and ethical dimensions of AI.

Figure 19 - Students working on their zines

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 4 - Methods used during the Lycée Michel Ange lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Group Discussion and Zine Making	Participants discussed their use of AI in daily life and education, then created zines to exchange with Greek partners, blending critical reflection with creative expression.
Onboard	Utopia/Dystopia Envisioning and Guidelines Creation	Students explored future scenarios for education in 30 years through small group

		discussions and developed guidelines for AI use in schools, presenting their ideas to peers.
Question	Group discussion on AI in school, work, and society	Collective reflection on where AI appears in everyday contexts and its perceived effects.
Question	Group discussion and Zine making (exchange with Greek partners)	Participants shared how they use AI in daily life and education, then created Zines to exchange internationally, blending critical reflection with creative expression.
Analyse		Examination of concrete examples of AI (ChatGPT, facial recognition), identifying risks and opportunities.
Analyse	Small group debates and scenario brainstorming	Students debated the benefits and dangers of AI, mapping possible scenarios collaboratively.
Envision	Zine-making workshops	Hands-on sessions where students designed Zine pages about desirable and undesirable AI futures.
Envision	Utopia/Dystopia envisioning	Students explored scenarios for education 30 years into the future, reflecting on positive and negative trajectories.
Envision	Guidelines creation	In groups, participants formulated guidelines for AI use in schools, which they then presented to peers.
Act	Collaborative exhibition of Zines	Exhibition featuring the zine output from the lab.
Reflect	Closing circle	Closing circle where participants reflected on the lab.

3.3.4 European Alternatives' Key Learnings & Impact

Across the three labs conducted by European Alternatives (Palermo, Pierrefitte, and Villeneuve), several key learnings emerged that highlight the adaptability of the Critical ChangeLab framework and the specific challenges of working with different age groups and themes.

1. **Effectiveness of creative methods** One major learning was the effectiveness of creative methods, particularly zine-making and video production, as tools for engaging participants in critical reflection. In Palermo, younger students

used short films to explore and challenge gender stereotypes, while in Pierrefitte and Villeneuve, zine-making encouraged personal expression and collective discussion around artificial intelligence. These creative outputs allowed participants to externalise complex ideas in accessible formats, fostering both individual ownership and group dialogue.

2. **Structure and age** Differences across age groups also generated important insights. With younger students in Palermo, facilitators noted the need for more structure and support to sustain engagement, whereas older participants in Villeneuve demonstrated greater autonomy and critical depth, linking AI debates to their educational and professional futures.

In terms of impact, the labs collectively demonstrated how participatory creative practices can enable youth to question social issues relevant to their lives, whether gender stereotypes or the implications of emerging technologies. Outputs such as short films and zines not only served as learning tools but also as artifacts that could be shared with peers, educators, and community members, amplifying the reach of participants' reflections. Importantly, students expressed that the experience helped them to articulate ideas about democracy, identity, and technology in ways that felt both meaningful and empowering.

Key performance indicators across the three labs confirm that EA met and, in some cases, exceeded its targets for youth participation, educator involvement, and civil society engagement. Palermo involved two sessions with middle-school students; Pierrefitte engaged younger high-school students; and Villeneuve worked with older high-school students. The labs reached a diverse group of participants, with outputs that reflect both age-specific concerns and common threads of democratic inquiry.

3.3.5 European Alternatives' Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between European Alternatives' CCLABs.

Table 5 - European Alternative's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	50
Participants from underrepresented groups	30
Educators	6
Other stakeholders	2
Researchers-facilitators	8
Number of participants (in final focus group)	10
Number of educators (in final interview)	4
Number of CSOs	3
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	3

3.4 LATRA (Greece)

LATRA conducted a CCLAB during PAR Cycle 3 with the Mytilene & Kalloni Elementary Schools.

3.4.1 Mytilene & Kalloni Elementary Schools

Geographical location	Mytilene and Kalloni, Lesvos, Greece
Demographic characteristics of participants	11-year-old schoolchildren from geographically remote rural location, low socio-economic background
Number of participants	160 children
Number of sessions	13 sessions between April and May 2025
Topic	Justice and Inclusion

LATRA’s PAR Cycle 3 lab continued the exploration of democratic values and citizenship among 11-year-old schoolchildren in Lesvos, Greece, building directly on the successful foundation established in PAR Cycle 2. Like PAR Cycle 2, the lab used an interactive, child-friendly adaptation of George Orwell’s *Animal Farm* as the central vehicle for exploring themes of power, justice, and democratic participation. However, PAR Cycle 3 expanded significantly beyond the single-school approach of PAR Cycle 2, implementing the programme across Kalloni and Mytilene Elementary Schools to reach a broader community of local and refugee children.

The core methodology maintained the successful interactive theatre approach where children actively participated by voting on character decisions and influencing the story’s outcome. This was complemented by creative workshops featuring drawing, role-play, and storytelling that helped children connect abstract democratic concepts to their lived experiences.

Figure 20 - Local and refugee children collaborate in a mixed-group creative workshop, using drawing, role-play, and storytelling to explore justice and inclusion

Based on comprehensive evaluation feedback from PAR 2 participants and educators, we made several key methodological improvements. First, we significantly reduced traditional classroom-style discussions, particularly the preparatory history lessons that PAR Cycle 2 participants found "less engaging" and "too similar to standard classroom lessons." Second, we restructured session openings to start with more interactive and creative activities rather than extended talking, directly responding to participant requests for "more hands-on activities." Third, we enhanced the workshop variety and frequency of creative elements, incorporating PAR Cycle 2 suggestions for "more games, physical activities" and "outdoor components."

Fourth, we expanded geographically from PAR Cycle 2's single-school implementation at Loutra Elementary to a multi-site approach across two schools, fulfilling our goal of engaging new stakeholders and communities. This expansion not only broadened participation, but also enriched the quality of conversations and peer interactions. By bringing together children from different parts of Lesvos, including those with varying cultural backgrounds, experiences with migration, and

educational environments, the sessions gained new depth. Children shared different views on justice and fairness, and facilitators observed that mixed-group discussions encouraged more critical reflection and empathy.

Figure 21 - Local and refugee children collaborate in a mixed-group creative workshop, using drawing, role-play, and storytelling to explore justice and inclusion

These changes were driven by direct participant feedback and evaluation insights from PAR Cycle 2. Participants explicitly stated that traditional teaching elements were the "least relevant" parts of the experience, while creative and interactive elements like the theatre performance and voting exercises were consistently identified as the most meaningful and impactful activities. PAR Cycle 2 participants specifically requested the ability to "create their own stories," "more frequent voting exercises," and "outdoor or crafting activities." Additionally, PAR Cycle 2's success at Loutra Elementary demonstrated the model's effectiveness and scalability potential, leading to our strategic decision to expand to multiple schools and engage additional stakeholders.

The methodological refinements led to enhanced engagement and deeper learning outcomes. By reducing traditional lecture-style elements and increasing experiential learning, children showed more sophisticated creative expression, moving from literal interpretation to generating alternative endings and symbolic representations of justice and equality. The expanded geographic reach

successfully fostered understanding between diverse groups across multiple school communities, with mixed-group sessions strengthening social bonds between local and refugee children. The enhanced creative approach enabled some children to propose real-world actions for their schools and communities, demonstrating early signs of transformative agency that built upon PAR 2's foundation of democratic understanding.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 12 - Methods used during the Mytiline & Kalloni Elementary Schools

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Recruiting stakeholders	Meetings with teachers, school administrators, NGO staff, and CSO representatives to present the objectives, secure support, and align activities with school needs.
Question	Focus groups with parents & teachers	Discussions with parents, teachers, and administrators to gather insights on existing attitudes towards refugees and democracy, and to identify challenges.
Analyse	Talking about democracy in the classroom	Teachers adapted lesson plans to highlight principles of equality, justice, and participation, connected to the refugee crisis. Activities included debates, role-play, and group discussions using textbooks, multimedia, and interactive exercises.
Envision & Examine	Theatre play: Animal Farm	A child-friendly adaptation of Orwell's <i>Animal Farm</i> . Children actively participated by voting on character decisions and engaging in reflection during the performance.
Act	Creative workshops after the play	Children explore real-world issues like the refugee crisis, themes of power, justice, and inclusion through creative activities, like role-playing, storytelling, drawing, and group problem-solving, that foster imagination and discussion around fairness and inclusive societies.
Reflect	Evaluative focus group	Facilitators lead focus groups where children reflect on their experiences, discuss democratic practices, and provide feedback to improve future interventions.

3.4.2 LATRA's Key Learnings & Impact

Four key learnings emerged during PAR Cycle 3. These include:

- 1) **Creative methodologies are essential for accessibility** Theatre, drawing, and role-play helped children connect emotionally and intellectually with complex democratic concepts that would otherwise remain abstract. The interactive Animal Farm performance was consistently identified as the most meaningful and impactful activity.
- 2) **Gradual development requires sustained engagement** Democratic engagement developed gradually through repeated, supportive activities. Children needed time and multiple opportunities to move from passive participation to recognizing their capacity to influence their environments collaboratively.
- 3) **Inclusive facilitation requires intentional strategies** Group dynamics sometimes limited inclusion, with louder voices dominating and refugee children initially holding back. This highlighted the need for more equitable facilitation strategies to ensure all voices are heard and valued.
- 4) **Real-world connections enhance learning** Children successfully linked themes like justice and power to their own school and community experiences, showing that abstract concepts become meaningful when connected to lived experiences. Some children began proposing real-life changes, demonstrating early signs of transformative agency.

Children showed clearer understanding of fairness, voice, and inclusion in both fictional and real-life contexts. They demonstrated increased ability to recognise inequalities and link narratives to real-life social dynamics. Many participants became more open to listening to different viewpoints and engaging in shared decision-making, with some proposing concrete actions like creating fairness groups or changing class decision-making processes.

Teachers reported greater openness to participatory, student-led approaches in the classroom. The experience prompted reflection on pedagogical practices, particularly regarding integration of democratic values. Educators observed that reserved students found their voice while more assertive students learned to share space, creating more balanced classroom dynamics.

The workshops fostered empathy and connection between local and refugee children, helping to bridge community divisions. Parents who were initially cautious grew more supportive as they observed positive changes in their children. The lab generated reusable materials and approaches that can inform future educational programming, creating lasting institutional change.

3.4.3 LATRA's Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged by LATRA.

Table 13 - LATRA's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	160
Participants from underrepresented groups	160
Educators	10
Other stakeholders	4
Researchers-facilitators	3
Number of participants (in final focus group)	7
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	2

3.5 Institute for Social Research (Croatia)

The Institute for Social Research conducted a three CCLAB labs during PAR Cycle 3 in three student dormitories in Zagreb – Dora Pejačević, Marija Jambrišak, and Novi Zagreb.

3.5.1 Dora Pejačević

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	Participants were high school students residing in the student dormitory “Dora Pejačević.” The group consisted of only female participants. Their age varied from 15 to 18 years old.
Number of participants	10
Number of sessions	7
Topic	Food waste / Throwing away food

This CCLAB was intended to be more educator-led, however researchers still had significant role in planning and conducting sessions. Unlike the previous cycle, participants were not given a predefined theme from which they should choose the topic and had full autonomy in selecting a topic that felt relevant and meaningful to their experiences. This change was introduced to encourage deeper engagement and to give them an opportunity to address the issues that they’ve encountered during their everyday life in a dormitory. This proved to be a valuable addition to the PAR cycle as it did indeed provide a significant boost to the participants engagement.

The onboarding session consisted of an activity – *Brainstorming*. During brainstorming, students identified a wide range of challenges and topics of interest they face in their everyday lives – both within their school and the dormitory, and even in the city. During the second session, participants, through *Idea Mapping*, narrowed these challenges and topics to the ones they found most relevant. Ultimately, they selected the topic of throwing away food. When they choose the topic, they explored it further through activity *5 whys?* where they identified various problems regarding the topic and their causes.

Figure 22 - 5whys? – identifying causes and consequences of throwing away food

In the following session they researched the topic, prepared and presented PowerPoint presentations, as well as prepared and organised questions for interviews they conducted between sessions. These interviews proved to be a valuable learning experience, as they allowed students to directly engage with others in their community (dormitory) and gain diverse perspectives on the issue.

In the following session, students engaged in a *Photovoice* activity. This visual method encouraged them to observe their surroundings more attentively and reflect on the concrete ways in which food waste manifests in everyday life. They were able to express their perspectives in creative ways and support one another in interpreting the broader social and environmental implications of the issue. Afterwards, the group participated in a *Future Scenarios* activity, however it revealed a lack of diverse perspectives - students tended to rely on similar viewpoints and had difficulty imagining alternative futures beyond their immediate experience.

A visit to the Red Cross provided them with direct experience and insight into real-world solutions to food waste. Additionally, by creating a zine, the students focused on addressing the problem within their own dormitory, proposing concrete and locally relevant actions.

Figure 23 - Visit to the Red Cross' food bank

The final session was dedicated to reflection. Participants expressed a high level of satisfaction with the entire CCLAB; however, the biggest challenge throughout the process was scheduling. Due to the end of the school year, many students were unable to attend several sessions.

Figure 24 - Zine about food waste in their dormitory

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 14 - Methods used during the Dora Pejačević lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Brainstorming	Participants discussed concerns and topics they wished to explore, guided by educators and researchers to identify potential focus areas for the project.
Question	Idea Mapping	Students collaboratively reviewed brainstormed topics and voted to select 'food waste' as the central theme for the PAR cycle.
Question	5 Whys	Participants analysed the root causes of food waste by iteratively asking 'why' for each symptom, using group diagrams to identify key contributing factors.

Analyse	Critical Cartography + Presentation	Small groups researched global and local food waste issues, created presentations, and shared insights to build critical understanding of the topic.
Analyse	Preparation of Interview Protocols	Groups developed questions and assigned roles for interviews with dormitory staff to gather diverse perspectives on food waste.
Examine & envision	Photovoice	Students captured and discussed photos representing food waste in their daily lives, using visual storytelling to deepen their engagement with the issue.
Examine & envision	Future Scenarios	Groups created optimistic, pessimistic, and realistic future scenarios on food waste using creative materials and presented their visions to peers.
Act	Presenting the Interviews	Students shared findings from interviews with dormitory staff, discussing insights about food waste management and prevention strategies.
Act	Design of the Zine	Participants created zines proposing measures and actions to address food waste, combining written and visual content for awareness-raising.
Act	Visit to Zagreb City Red Cross Society	A field visit introduced students to food bank operations and food donation processes as strategies to reduce food waste.
Act	Zine Presentation	Students presented their completed zines to peers and discussed their ideas for practical action on food waste.

3.5.2 Marija Jambrisak

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	Participants were high school students residing in the student dormitory "Učenički dom Marije Jambrišak." The group consisted of only female participants. Their age varied from 15 to 18 years old.
Number of participants	13
Number of sessions	7
Topic	Mental health - self-perception and expectations of others

This CCLAB was largely participant- and educator-led, with minimal interference from researchers. Unlike previous cycles, participants were not given a predefined theme, allowing them full autonomy in selecting a topic that felt relevant and meaningful to their lived experiences. This change was introduced to encourage deeper engagement and to foster a more trusting, open dialogue between students and their educator – conversations that might not have emerged in the presence of researchers. As a result, discussions became more personal, reflective, and emotionally resonant, with students sharing their authentic thoughts and experiences around the chosen issue.

The onboarding session featured two key activities: *brainstorming* and *idea mapping*. During brainstorming, students identified a wide range of challenges they face in their everyday lives – both within their school and the dormitory. Through idea mapping, the group collaboratively narrowed these challenges to the ones they found most relevant and actionable. Ultimately, they selected the topic of mental health. The second session further refined this focus, leading to a group decision to explore the issue of self-perception and the impact of others' expectations.

Figure 25 - Participants discussing and analysing different external and internal influences on self-image

In the following session, students worked to unpack ideals of beauty - how these are socially constructed, reinforced by internal and external influences, and often gendered. This helped them recognize patterns in how beauty standards are formed and perpetuated. To deepen their understanding, participants attended the theatre performance *Girls with Horns*, which explores women's mental health and identity. The play had a profound emotional impact, sparking a rich and honest discussion in the next session.

Figure 26 - Participants and researchers after attending theatre play Girls with Horns

Inspired by the themes of the play and their own experiences, students decided to implement a creative intervention: designing and displaying motivational stickers throughout the dormitory. These stickers, featuring inspiring messages and images created by the students themselves, were intended to promote a more positive self-image among their peers. In the following session, participants finalised their designs, and in the session after that, they collectively placed the stickers in areas where they believed they would have the greatest effect.

The final session was dedicated to reflection. Participants expressed a high level of satisfaction with the CCLAB, appreciating the freedom to choose their topic, the depth of the discussions, the creative process, and the tangible outcome of their efforts.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 15 – Methods used during the Marija Jambrisak lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Brainstorming	Educators facilitated a group discussion where students identified personal concerns and topics they wished to explore in the PAR cycle.
Onboard	Idea Mapping	In small groups, students selected and debated preferred topics, leading to a democratic vote where 'mental health' was chosen as the cycle's focus.
Question	9 Statements – 3 Groups	Students rotated between groups analysing subtopics on mental health, ultimately consolidating themes into a single focus topic through discussion and voting.
Analyse	Ideals of Beauty (Mobile Search & Presentation)	Students used their phones to select images reflecting beauty standards, shared their reasoning, and discussed the social and psychological aspects of self-image.
Analyse	Ideals of Beauty (Silhouette Exercise)	Groups identified external and internal factors of beauty using annotated silhouettes, fostering reflection on self-respect and societal expectations.
Examine & Envision	Attending Theatre Play – 'Girls with Horns'	Participants attended a theatre performance related to mental health themes and engaged in pre- and post-show discussions to deepen understanding.
Examine & Envision	Debate on Activity Design	Students synthesized their knowledge and debated potential activities, ultimately selecting a gallery exhibition to promote positive self-perception.
Act	Material Preparation for Gallery	Participants created inspirational drawings and messages that were scanned and prepared as stickers for their student dormitory gallery.
Act	Discussion and Sticker Placement	Students collaboratively decided on sticker locations and walked through the dormitory to install them, reinforcing agency and teamwork.
Evaluate & Reflect	Final Overview and Reflection	In groups, participants shared reflections on their PAR journey, highlighting lessons learned, emotional growth, and applications to daily life.

3.5.3 Novi Zagreb

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia
Demographic characteristics of participants	Participants were upper secondary school students residing in the student dormitory “Učenički dom Novi Zagreb.” The group was gender-diverse, including both male and female students. Their ages ranged from 15 to 18 years, representing various grade levels and backgrounds.
Number of participants	11
Number of sessions	7
Topic	Drug use and addiction among students living in student dormitory

This CCLAB was a lot more in control of the participants (students) and educators with minimal interference from the researchers. Participants were not given an overarching theme to guide their choice but were completely free to choose their own topic. The content of the sessions was also slightly changed, with reduced emphasis on structured interactive methods, and focused mainly on debate and discussion as means of conducting the sessions. These changes took the feedback that we got from the UDNZ students at the end of the previous PAR cycle into account. As a result, participants were more engaged and motivated to participate, making their discussions a lot more dynamic. The group as a whole was more dynamic as well since all of the participants were motivated to be the part of the PAR cycle.

The onboarding session served primarily to introduce participants to the project and the dynamics of the PAR cycle. Following an engaging *icebreaker activity* and informal introductions, participants engaged in an *open discussion* on possible topics for their cycle. After thoughtful consideration, identifying various problems in their community, and narrowing the options down to three key issues, the group collectively voted to focus on the topic of drug use and addiction.

The second session delved deeper into this chosen topic, with participants exploring various social, psychological, and personal dimensions and perspectives. This session encouraged participants to reflect on their own experiences or

observations, enabling a broader understanding of the issue's complexity. The result was a somewhat heated debate between two main sides – those that focused mainly on sanctions, and those focused on prevention of substance abuse.

Figure 27 - Participants during the session "Examine & Envision"

The third session served mainly as a presentation of different insights related to the topic such as the causes of the problem, effects of THC use, different misconceptions, etc. During the fourth session, the group focused on how they could collaboratively address drug use and addiction through teamwork as well as envisioning concrete ways to address the issue. At this point, participants began to fully grasp the complexity of addiction and acknowledged their limitations as students in tackling such a multifaceted issue directly.

Figure 28 - Participants and educator during the session "Act"

This insight was further deepened in the fifth session, when they attended a performance by Croatian rapper Marin Ivanović "Stoka," who shared his personal journey with addiction and how it inspired him to create his testimony show. His story was a powerful catalyst, offering an authentic perspective that resonated deeply with participants. In the sixth session, the group collectively decided on a realistic and impactful intervention: the implementation of a "Night Living Room" - a welcoming space within the dormitory where students can socialize, build connections, and feel less isolated. The goal was to foster inclusion and mitigate the risk factors associated with loneliness and substance use. The final session offered space for reflection, where participants shared their thoughts on the CCLAB expressing strong satisfaction with their engagement and the outcomes achieved.

Figure 29 - Performance by Croatian rapper Marin Ivanović "Stoka"

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 16 - Methods used during the Novi Zagreb lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Getting to Know Each Other – Identity Swap	Participants stand in a circle, adopt each other's identities after introductions, and introduce themselves as that person to promote familiarity and group cohesion.
Onboard	Problem Selection	Participants reviewed pre-printed topics, added their own, discussed them, and voted to select a specific issue for the PAR cycle.

Question	Debate	Students debated a thesis on marijuana use, split into groups to construct arguments, and engaged in a structured exchange of viewpoints with a role-playing exercise.
Question	Never Have I Ever	Participants responded to topic-related statements by stepping forward if they had experienced the situation, sparking reflection and conversation on substance use.
Analyse	Association Game	Participants formed a circle and rapidly shared associations with words related to substance use to stimulate spontaneous thinking and creativity.
Analyse	Presentation and Discussion	An informative session on cannabis was followed by a video and facilitated discussion where participants contributed their experiences and insights.
Examine & envision	Brainstorming	Participants generated and categorized ideas for potential dormitory interventions to prevent substance abuse and support students at risk.
Act	A Play by Croatian Rapper Marin Ivanović "Stoka"	Students attended a theatrical performance and discussion led by a rapper sharing personal experiences with drug use and recovery.
Act	Discussion about the Play	A follow-up discussion explored students' impressions, performance analysis, and connections between the play's themes and their own lives.
Act	Designing an Intervention	Building on prior sessions, participants planned actions to foster social inclusion and prevent drug use within their dormitory community.
Evaluate & reflect	Closing Debate	Participants reflected on PAR Cycle 3, comparing it to previous cycles, and shared concluding thoughts in a group discussion.

3.5.4 Key Learnings & Impact

Four key learnings emerged from ISRZ's CCLABs.

1. **Voice & autonomy are crucial.** Young people want to have a voice and influence their environment but often lack opportunities to express their opinions and take meaningful action. Their transformative agency can be developed when provided with sufficient time, resources, and when motivated. Across all three labs, participants selected topics that were personally

meaningful, with minimal intervention from educators and researchers—highlighting the importance of autonomy in decision-making and its strong positive (perhaps even crucial) effect on participant motivation.

2. **Hands-on methods work** Participants responded especially well to hands-on, creative methods such as photovoice, future scenarios, and zine-making, while lectures and school-like tasks were less effective. Community-based activities, including visits to the Red Cross (UDDP), attending a theatre play (UDMJ), and a session with Croatian rapper Marin Ivanović “Stoka” (UDNZ), proved highly impactful, helping participants connect their topics to real-world contexts.
3. **Safe environments are critical** Establishing a safe and supportive environment was also essential, especially when addressing sensitive and personal topics. While this heavily depended on the dynamic between educators and participants, successful facilitation allowed for open dialogue, which contributed positively to participants’ self-perception, reduced feelings of isolation, and fostered deeper connections among peers.
4. **Timing is a challenge** As all labs took place at the end of the school year, this limited some participants’ involvement because of overwhelming school-related obligations. Conducting CCLABs near the end of the school year is challenging.

The three labs led to tangible and lasting impacts within their respective dormitory communities. At UDNZ, the creation of the “Night Living Room” provided a new, dedicated space for students to socialise, addressing a previously overlooked need for connection and community within the dormitory. This initiative raised awareness among both educators and students about the risks of isolation and loneliness, and it holds long-term potential to foster friendships and reduce the likelihood of harmful behaviours such as substance abuse.

At UDMJ, participants designed and placed inspirational stickers throughout the dorm to promote positive self-image, self-esteem, and self-perception. With the support of dormitory staff, these stickers will remain in place, continuing to impact future generations. The lab also deepened educators’ understanding of the self-perception challenges young girls in the dormitory face.

Meanwhile, at UDDP, students created zines to raise awareness about food waste and responsible consumption. These zines will be distributed to future dorm residents, helping to promote more thoughtful food-related behaviours. The initiative has inspired dorm staff to consider adopting zine-making as a regular practice for encouraging peer-to-peer learning and positive change. Overall, all three labs managed to make an impact on three levels: participant, educator and community.

3.5.5 Institute for Social Research Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between Institute for Social Research’s CCLABs.

Table 17 - Institute for Social Research’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	34
Participants from underrepresented groups	34
Educators	7
Other stakeholders	3
Researchers-facilitators	7
Number of participants (in final focus group)	23
Number of educators (in final interview)	1
Number of CSOs	1
Number of formal education organizations	0
Number of non-formal education organizations	0

3.6 Ars Electronica (Austria)

Ars Electronica conducted three labs during PAR Cycle 3 – one with a school, Europaschule Linz, and two with community organisations, Verein Saum and Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner.

3.6.1 Europaschule Linz

Geographical location	Linz, Upper Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	14 male, 8 female, diverse backgrounds, aged between 14 and 15 years old, middle school
Number of participants	22
Number of sessions	4
Topic	Conflict resolution strategies in the classroom

Following consultations with the class educator, it became evident that conflict resolution was a major challenge within the student group. Key concerns included frequent disruptions, poor self-regulation, and a gender imbalance in discussions, where male students dominated conversations and female students participated less. These issues impacted classroom communication and mutual respect. In response, the CCLAB focused on the topic of conflict management strategies – in opposition to a more open topic in PAR Cycle 2 (“Envisioning Futures”). This PAR Cycle also veered away from producing podcasts to focusing on video production as this seemed more appropriate to the age group. A CCLAB was developed to help students explore better conflict management strategies and culminate in the creation of a Classroom Agreement. This agreement, intended to be signed by both students and teachers and presented to the Student Parliament, aimed to empower students in shaping classroom rules and expectations.

Figure 30 – Still from a speculative video produced by participants about conflict resolution

Even though the students were engaged in the various methods and video production task that explored various speculative scenarios for conflicts within the classroom, the idea of a classroom agreement on conflict management strategies was met with significant resistance with students pointing towards teacher's responsibilities to manage conflict. In their opinion, the hierarchical structure of the school came with responsibilities for teaching staff – not students – one of which was to manage the classroom. To accept the students' position and give them space to express their opinion without enforcing existing hierarchical structures via a signed classroom agreement, facilitators instead tried to validate their position and agency in the classroom. This led to a nuanced reflection about hierarchies, responsibilities and the school environment – and a joint decision to not produce a classroom agreement.

Figure 31 – Still from a speculative video produced by participants about conflict resolution

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 18 – Methods used during Europaschule Linz lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Icebreaker – Getting to Know Each Other	This physical activity helps participants connect by grouping themselves based on criteria like height or birthdate, encouraging spontaneous interaction and conversation
Question & Analyse	Reflections on School Life	Students reflect on their school experiences using post it notes on thematic posters, followed by group discussions exploring how perceptions influence school dynamics.
Question & Analyse	Empathy Exercise – Understanding Perspectives in School Life through Video Analysis	Participants analyse a humorous video on school conflict to reflect on various roles involved and relate them to personal experience, then develop additional scenarios in groups.
Question & Analyse	Meme-Making	Students collaboratively create and share memes that depict school conflict scenarios, using humour and creativity to reflect on perspectives and behaviours.
Question & Analyse	Survey about Conflicts in School	An anonymous yes/no survey gathers students’ views on school conflict, with results collectively reviewed and discussed to prompt awareness and dialogue.

Analyse	Yes/No Icebreakers on School Conflicts	Participants express their opinions by physically positioning themselves in 'yes' or 'no' zones in response to conflict-related questions, promoting open discussion.
Envision & examine	Worksheet on Conflict Resolution Scenarios	Students work in groups to analyse conflict cases and develop ideal resolutions, which they then briefly present to the whole class.
Envision & examine	Video Creation on Conflict Resolution Strategies	Building on previous activities, students script and record short videos in varied formats to creatively present solutions to school conflict scenarios.
Envision & examine	Reverse brainstorming	Using previously recorded videos, students brainstorm actions that worsen conflict situations and identify common triggers, leading to constructive solutions.
Act & reflect	Strategies for Conflict Resolution & Voting	Facilitators and students propose, test, and vote on techniques for classroom conflict resolution, selecting practical strategies for implementation.

3.6.2 Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner

Geographical location	Traun, Upper Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	15 male, 2 female, various backgrounds, rural Austria, aged 17-18
Number of participants	17
Number of sessions	2
Topic	Envisioning Futures

Ars Electronica partnered with Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner, a non-formal education centre for unemployed youth (ages 14–18) – contrary to previous PAR cycles where AE partnered with more traditional, formal education environments – for a CCLAB on “Envisioning Futures”. This topic was determined as educators observed that many young people struggled to envision alternatives and to recognize their own agency in shaping the future. The workshops showed a mixed picture of engagement. On the one hand, participants were often reluctant to speculate about the future or to engage in exercises, finding it difficult to connect creative prompts to their own lives. Their concentration sometimes wavered, and they expressed doubts about the practical impact of their contributions. On the other hand, moments of openness and insight emerged: they acknowledged that

individual actions can inspire meaningful change, and once trust was built, they shared personal frustrations and perspectives freely.

Figure 32 - Participants brainstorming their episodes at Schulungszentrum

The turning point came during the podcast production phase. Moving into a professional recording studio generated excitement and motivation, with participants taking the task seriously, re-recording to improve their performance, and adding music to enhance the episodes. For many, the realization that their voices would be published and accessible was empowering, leading them to take ownership of their work and express pride in their results. Overall, producing podcast episodes, in particular, proved to be effective for engagement, giving participants a tangible outlet to voice their perspectives.

Figure 33 – Participants working on their podcast episodes in the recording studio at Ars Electronica Center

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 19 – Methods used during the Schulungszentrum Weidinger & Partner lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding	Icebreaker Line-up + Yes/No	Participants positioned themselves in line-ups and room corners in response to prompts, moving from personal questions to content-driven discussions on societal issues.
Question & Analyse	Frustration Mapping	Using Mentimeter, students submitted responses to open-ended questions about daily frustrations and future visions, which facilitators analysed with them.
Question, Envision & Examine	Future Exhibition	Participants explored historical visions of the future through images and videos, reflected on themes using post-its, and brainstormed podcast topics in groups.
Examine & Act	Planning a Podcast Episode	Groups used concept worksheets to define podcast topics and outline content structure based on insights from the Future Exhibition activity.

Examine & Act	Continued Podcast Planning	Students refined podcast scripts, collaborated on content organization, and used ChatGPT to brainstorm and structure ideas before recording.
Act	Recording episodes in Sound Studio – Open Lab	Students recorded podcast episodes in a professional studio, gaining confidence and developing communication skills through repeated practice.

3.6.3 Verein Saum

Geographical location	Perg/ Linz surroundings, Upper Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	16–18 years of age, many of them with mental conditions and from challenging socio-economic backgrounds, rural area; 14 male, 2 female
Number of participants	16
Number of sessions	4
Topic	The Future of Work

This CCLAB engaged with socially vulnerable adolescents aged 16–18 at Verein Saum, an initiative in rural Austria that offers structure, social belonging, and daily purpose to unemployed youth – contrary to the collaborations with more formal learning environments in PAR Cycle 2. The workshops showed that many participants struggle to imagine their futures, especially connected to their work life, a difficulty intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic, which left them focused mainly on the near term. Educators observed that the young people often lacked a sense of agency and found it hard to picture themselves in different situations, linking this to limited transformative competences and uncertainty about how to intervene in their lives or communities. This challenge informed the choice of the topic “The Future of Work.”

Across four sessions, activities encouraged participants to reflect on work and the skills it requires. Despite initial shyness, the group joined actively and showed openness in discussing personal struggles, including loneliness, family tensions, and mental health challenges. Their willingness to speak candidly stood out. A strong recurring theme was their desire for independence: many wished to live on their own, supported by stable jobs and financial security, but worried about money, employment, and housing. These practical concerns dominated their reflections

more than abstract future visions. Maintaining engagement and concentration was sometimes difficult, and several participants struggled to connect creative or abstract exercises to their lives. While a few imagined fantastical scenarios such as flying cars, many found it challenging to develop realistic career projections or link broader societal issues to their situations. Still, their openness to sharing highlighted both vulnerabilities and trust in the group environment.

Figure 34 - Participants editing their podcast episode

The final stage involved creating a podcast. Building on earlier reflections, participants worked in small groups to plan and record episodes, freely choosing themes, structures, and roles. Sessions at Ars Electronica Center's sound studio enabled them to record several episodes and a jointly produced introduction with music. Many re-recorded their content, improving delivery and style. The activity was highly engaging: even hesitant students became involved, showing enthusiasm and ownership. Overall, the podcast project in particular gave them a platform to take ownership, build confidence, and articulate their perspectives.

Figure 35 - Participants in the recording booth

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 20 - Methods used during the Verein SAUM AusbildungsFit Arbeitsraum lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding	Introduction Project – Presentation / Data Consent Explanation	Participants were introduced to the project and facilitators, and the consent process was explained to ensure understanding and agreement.
Onboarding	Icebreaker – Line-up/Yes or No	Participants positioned themselves in response to prompts, starting with personal questions and progressing to societal issues to encourage nuanced discussion.
Question & Analyse	Frustrations Brainstorming	Using Mentimeter, participants shared concerns about daily life and future aspirations, creating a word cloud to identify themes for future sessions.
Onboarding	Creating a Podcast Intro	Participants engaged in body percussion and vocal exercises, then collaboratively designed a musical podcast intro using a digital tool.

Onboarding	Icebreaker: Body percussion exercise	A warm-up activity using body percussion to activate concentration and re-engage participants with elements from previous sessions.
Question, Envision & Examine	Future Exhibition	Students explored images of future scenarios, reflected on job-related skills, and grouped ideas thematically to encourage critical thinking.
Question, Envision & Examine	Postcards from the Future	Participants created visual postcards depicting their imagined futures of work, responding to an earlier exchange from Irish students.
Onboarding	Mazunga - Voice & Movement Warm-Up	A group vocal and movement exercise designed to energize participants and build a sense of collaboration through rhythm and timing.
Reflect	Voting & discussion of competences	Students voted on CCLAB competences for future work relevance and discussed their choices, encouraging reflection and value-based reasoning.
Examine & Act	Creating a podcast episode	In groups, students planned and recorded podcast episodes on themes they identified, fostering creativity and teamwork in a professional studio setting.
Act	Podcast Editing and Finalization – Open Lab	Participants edited their podcasts using Descript, created cover images, and prepared content for publication on Spotify.

3.6.4 Ars Electronica’s Key Learnings & Impact

One of the key insights were that creative/art methods are not common in many learning environments and therefore many participants found it hard to engage and see the benefit of creative tasks. Across the groups, speculative discussions about the future were difficult for participants to connect to their own lives and they often disengaged or defaulted to unrealistic scenarios. However, when creative tasks were embedded in tangible, real-world contexts - especially in inspiring settings like the professional sound studio - their motivation and output increased significantly. Another takeaway was the crucial part creating a safe space played. Participants were initially shy or resistant, but once a safe and supportive environment was established, they shared personal challenges (loneliness, mental health, family issues) with striking honesty.

The CCLABS offered socially vulnerable adolescents a safe and supportive space to

explore their futures, reflect on personal challenges, and develop skills such as creativity, communication, empathy, and adaptability. While many initially struggled to envision realistic paths or assert their agency, arts methods, structured discussions and the podcast project enabled them to take ownership of their work, collaborate effectively, and gain confidence in expressing their ideas and perspectives.

3.6.4 Ars Electronica’s Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between Ars Electronica’s CCLABs.

Table 21 - Ars Electronica’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	53
Participants from underrepresented groups	50
Educators	8
Other stakeholders	2
Researchers-facilitators	2
Number of participants (in final focus group)	8
Number of educators (in final interview)	0
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	1
Number of non-formal education organizations	3

3.7 Kersnikova (Slovenia)

Kersnikova completed a CCLAB with Skupna točka – Medgeneracijski center, a humanitarian organisation.

3.7.1 DemoBot

Geographical location	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Demographic characteristics of participants	11 – 15 years old 2/3 of participants were boys
Number of participants	34
Number of sessions	8
Topic	Exploring the role of technology in democracy. Imagining a democratic robot as well as designing and implementing its features.

Originally envisioned as a series of workshops culminating in youth co-creating a conversational robot - the “DemoBot” - to explore democratic practices through AI, the CCLAB underwent a significant change in planned activities but stayed close to the general topic. Initiated by Zavod Kersnikova at the Skupna Točka community center in Ljubljana, the workshops aimed to introduce 11-15 year-olds to democratic concepts using technology as both a tool and subject of inquiry. The plan diverged from the initial idea of designing and building a physical robot chat bot to designing a board game about democracy that uses a technical gadget as one of the game mechanics. This was due to participant’s input as well as time constraints. Key activities included discussions about and with AI on democracy, collaborative designing of a game, and STEM activities (programming Arduino UNO, 3D modelling in tinker-cad and soldering).

Figure 36 - Participants preparing papers with questions for their board game, alongside the breadboarded prototypes of a voting device

Whereas the PAR Cycle 2 format was very open with the participants themselves deciding on a topic based on what they perceived was a problem in the society, we decided to choose the topic in advance for PAR Cycle 3, because this allowed us better preparation and because topic decision took a lot of time in PAR Cycle 2 that could be dedicated to other activities. For PAR Cycle 3 we chose a topic closely

related to the one chosen by PAR Cycle 2 participants. The outcome was more focused as a result, while still delegating the participants some power to influence the plan of the workshops.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 22 – Methods used during Skupna točka – Medgeneracijski center lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Discussing democracy with AI	Participants explore democracy and its connection to technology through AI tools and guided discussions.
Question	Understanding the world of electronics and sensors	An interactive session introduces basic electronics and sensor technology, with hands-on demonstrations and discussions on real-world applications.
Analyse	Basics of programming using Tinkercad	Students learn block-based programming logic and simulate circuits in Tinkercad through guided exercises and collaborative problem-solving.
Envision & Examine	3D modelling using Tinkercad	Participants design simple 3D models and explore design thinking concepts, preparing objects for potential 3D printing.
Envision & Examine	Mastering soldering	This hands-on workshop teaches safe soldering techniques and circuit assembly through the creation of a voting terminal prototype.
Act	Designing and making a game console with the help of LLMs	Students collaborate to design a game console, using LLMs for ideation and planning, and democratically selecting features.
Act	Programming the game console with games that address democratic values	Participants program games for the console, focusing on mechanics that promote democratic principles like cooperation and fair play.
Act	Bug fixing, reflection and final meeting	A concluding session where students fix bugs, reflect on the PAR cycle, celebrate achievements, and discuss applying democratic values in daily life.

3.7.2 Key Learnings and Impact

Three key learnings emerged from the CCLAB:

1. **Adaption to context** Adapting the CCLAB activities to the specific situation – including the place, the participants, and other contextual factors – is essential. In this case, the workshops took place in a community centre where children were accustomed to other routines, such as doing homework, studying, or playing with friends, often alone or in small groups. These children required a different approach to engagement than participants who arrive at workshops with clear expectations, for example after their parents have explained what the session will involve.
2. **Order of activities** One of the goals of this lab was to deliver Voices of Youth videos, short films made by participants where they express their views on democracy. Because of the internal deadline for delivering the videos, the filming was planned for the very first session. This proved to be a bad decision as it made some participants feel uncomfortable and reluctant to take part in it, and a number of them did not return for subsequent workshops. It would have been preferable to carry out the filming at the end of the program, when participants were already more comfortable with speaking about this topic.
3. **Responsiveness to participants' interests** After the onboarding session, it became clear that the original topic was too difficult and not very engaging for the participants. Educators decided to change the programme to focus more on the children's interests, which led to much higher engagement and creativity.

The main impact of the CCLAB was the demonstration that the format of workshops developed in the previous PAR cycles can work well in a completely different context with a different group of participants. The students experienced and were introduced to methods and topics they were not used to. They were proud of the game they made and said that they will play it with their peers thus spreading the discussion about democracy beyond the scope of the lab.

The CCLAB was also a positive experience for the community centre Skupna Točka as they saw it as a way of diversifying their program and offering the children topics and activities that are underrepresented in the program of the community

centre. Educators were happy with the end result and found the challenge an opportunity for personal growth.

3.7.3 Kersnikova’s Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between Kersnikova’s CCLABs.

Table 23 – Kersnikova’s KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	36
Participants from underrepresented groups	12
Educators	2
Other stakeholders	1
Researchers-facilitators	1
Number of participants (in final focus group)	3
Number of educators (in final interview)	1
Number of CSOs	2
Number of formal education organizations	0
Number of non-formal education organizations	3

3.8 Waag Futurelab (Netherlands)

Waag Futurelab (Waag) completed two labs during PAR Cycle 3 - one with the secondary school Don Bosco and one with the secondary school Damstede Lyceum. Reports on both labs are described below.

3.8.1 Don Bosco

Geographical location	Volendam, Netherlands
Demographic characteristics of participants	Girls aged 14-15, in their third year of VMBO level education. The school is located in Volendam, a small fishing village with a distinct local culture. Volendam is in the province of North Holland.
Number of participants	16
Number of sessions	4
Topic	Disinformation and democracy

The Critical ChangeLab at Don Bosco took place over four sessions, each aimed at deepening students’ understanding of disinformation and its impact on democracy while fostering critical, creative, and agency-based competences. The lab’s participants were 16 girls, aged 14-15, in their third year of VMBO ‘kader’ level education. The setting of Volendam, with its distinct local culture, added context to the activities and reflections. Compared to PAR Cycle 2, one major change we implemented was the stronger emphasis on creative, hands-on methods right from the start as well as a theme that was more concretely chosen; the theme immediately connected to their world of experience, but did not come as close to them personally as the theme of identity. In PAR Cycle 2, more time had been dedicated to discussions and abstract reflection, which proved challenging given students’ hesitations with open dialogue. For PAR Cycle 3, we chose to integrate making and doing earlier and more frequently, as we observed that this cohort of students engaged more deeply when they could express knowledge through tangible outputs rather than purely verbal participation. This change was crucial in improving both engagement and depth of reflection.

The lab began with introductory activities designed to break the ice and build rapport. We used short videos and direct questions about social media use to start conversations around disinformation. However, initial discussions highlighted that

students were reserved and gave socially desirable answers, avoiding deeper reflection. The first noticeable shift occurred when we introduced *Escape Fake*, an augmented reality game that allows students to engage with disinformation detection in a playful, interactive way. The use of AR technology tapped into their familiarity with mobile devices, creating immediate motivation and focus.

In the second session, we focused on critical evaluation through a *Fake or Real challenge* where students analysed various media examples. They enjoyed identifying fake news, especially when it connected to their lived experiences on social media. This was followed by creating *short reels* to explore how disinformation affects personal lives. Allowing phone use for this task was highly effective; students felt comfortable and enthusiastic, and the activity surfaced reflections on real-world impacts, such as bullying and damaged friendships.

The third session marked a turning point. Through the *filter bubble mood board* activity, students visually mapped their social media ecosystems. This creative exercise facilitated a profound moment: a student shared her experience of being trapped in a distressing content loop, sparking genuine peer discussion on how algorithms can erode choice and agency. This demonstrated how the shift toward making and visualisation helped connect abstract concepts to their realities.

Figure 37 - Students working on their Filter Bubble mood boards

Figure 38 - Students working on their Filter Bubble mood boards

In the final session, students *co-designed or modified familiar games* (e.g., Jenga, Memory) to raise awareness of disinformation among younger audiences. They were given the assignment to design a game to make 12–13-year-old students aware of disinformation. This made it easier for them, since they could still strongly identify with the target group, while at the same time being just distant enough for it not to become too personal. This hands-on creation fostered a strong sense of ownership and responsibility. The activity allowed them to reflect on their role as potential change-makers. Playing each other's games and exchanging feedback further deepened understanding and reinforced collaborative values.

Figure 39 - Game design template used by students

The deliberate shift from discussion-heavy methods in PAR Cycle 2 to more creative, making-oriented activities in PAR Cycle 3 directly contributed to stronger engagement, more personal connections to the topic, and visible growth in critical and agency-related competences. The balance of playful learning and serious reflection was key in helping students grasp the complex links between disinformation, democracy, and their own agency.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 24 - Methods used during Don Bosco lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Discussion - Getting to know each other	This method introduces participants to the topic of disinformation through a short video and guided group discussion about their familiarity and experiences.
Onboard	Discussion - Understanding the game and terminology	Students receive a brief explanation of disinformation concepts and collaboratively explore the Escape Fake AR game to learn by solving interactive puzzles.
Question & Analyse	Discussion in small groups	Facilitators lead intimate group conversations where students reflect on their social media use and the presence of disinformation in their digital lives.
Question & Analyse	Fake or real	Students analyse a series of media items and debate whether they are real or fake, supporting their choices with reasoning.
Envision & examine	Short reels: reels about the impact of fake news on your life	Participants create short social media videos that express how fake news affects them, combining personal reflection with digital storytelling.
Envision & examine	Filter Bubble	Students map their digital environment by identifying brands and influencers they follow, then make a collage to visualize and discuss their personal filter bubbles.
Act & reflect	Remake an existing game	Participants redesign familiar games like Jenga or Twister to incorporate themes of disinformation, promoting learning through creative adaptation and play.

3.8.2 Damstede Lyceum

Geographical location	Amsterdam Noord, Netherlands
Demographic characteristics of participants	High level high school students; 60% boys, 40% girls. The school is located in Amsterdam North, an area in

	Amsterdam where the social economic status is vulnerable.
Number of participants	17
Number of sessions	3
Topic	Disinformation and democracy

The Critical Change Lab at Damstede Lyceum took place over three sessions and centred on game design as a means of exploring disinformation and its impact on democracy. The group, consisting of 17 VWO students with diverse backgrounds and interests, engaged in a learning journey that combined critical reflection, creative making, and collaboration.

Similar to the Don Bosco lab, we iterated on what we learned in PAR Cycle 2 to inform PAR Cycle 3. In PAR Cycle 2, the emphasis had been on guided discussions and analysis of disinformation examples, but this approach revealed limitations in sustaining engagement across all students. For PAR Cycle 3, we shifted the balance: we placed stronger focus on co-creation and maker activities as the main method of inquiry and reflection. The decision to introduce game design as a core element was driven by two reasons. First, we observed that these students worked well with creative challenges and had clear affinities with design processes. Second, we wanted to foster greater ownership and agency by inviting them to create something meaningful for others - in this case, younger peers.

The lab began with *discussions designed to break the ice* and introduce the topic. The first session saw lively exchanges, including a debate sparked by one student's claim that COVID-19 was disinformation. While controversial, this opened up valuable space for dialogue and helped the group explore how differing perspectives shape understanding of facts. The introduction of the AR game *Escape Fake* was a key moment. It provided an accessible entry point to experience the real-world consequences of disinformation. The competitive element of the game kept motivation high and encouraged collaboration.

In the second session, we moved further into the co-creation process. Students worked in small groups to design their own games about disinformation. This required them to define a target audience, objectives, and gameplay principles. For many, this was both exciting and challenging. Some groups quickly generated

ideas and worked with enthusiasm; others struggled to align their visions and coordinate their efforts. Facilitators intentionally took a step back, providing guidance without taking over, allowing students to own the design process.

Figure 40 - Games developed by students - Perspectives Game (L) and Fake or Real (R)

The final session focused on testing and refining. Groups played each other's games and provided feedback, with particular attention to clarity of instructions and relevance for the intended younger audience. The students played with great energy and took pride in sharing their creations. Reflective conversations followed, with many students noting how their understanding of disinformation's societal impact had deepened, particularly its potential to undermine justice and democratic processes.

Figure 41 - Students testing one another's games

By prioritising design and making over purely analytical exercises, this change from PAR Cycle 2 contributed to stronger engagement and richer outcomes. The students felt taken seriously and embraced their role as educators of younger peers. They expressed greater awareness of disinformation's dangers and reported feeling a stronger sense of responsibility to act. The combination of creative freedom and critical reflection enabled students not only to think about disinformation but also to imagine ways to counter it.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 25 - Methods used during Damstede Lyceum lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboard	Discussion - Getting to know each other	This activity introduces participants to one another and to the topic of disinformation through guided

		questions and a shared video featuring peer responses.
Onboard	Playing an AR game	Participants play 'Escape Fake,' an augmented reality game where they work to undo a wrongful conviction caused by disinformation, experiencing its societal impacts.
Question & Analyse	Fake news or just nothing? Creating a news broadcast	In this group activity, participants create a news broadcast using both real and fake news stories, challenging peers to distinguish between them.
Question & Analyse	Fake or real	This method involves analysing various media items to determine whether they are fake or real, encouraging critical discussion and reasoning.
Act & Reflect	Design your own disinformation game	Participants co-design an original game on disinformation, considering gameplay elements and audience, to promote awareness and creative engagement with the topic.
Act & Reflect	Playing each other's games	Groups exchange and play one another's self-designed games, offering empathetic feedback while considering a younger target audience.

3.8.3 Key Learnings & Impact

Throughout the labs at both Don Bosco and Damstede Lyceum, four key learnings emerged:

1. **Creative making boosts engagement** Creative, maker-based methods are powerful tools for engaging students with complex topics like disinformation and democracy. When students could design and build their own games, their motivation, ownership, and depth of reflection increased significantly compared to more discussion-based approaches.
2. **Real audiences drive responsibility** Working for a real target audience of younger peers created a sense of responsibility and agency. This external focus encouraged students to think carefully about how to make their messages clear and impactful.
3. **Collaboration requires support** While some groups thrived, others struggled to align their ideas or divide tasks effectively. It highlighted the need for additional support in team dynamics and project management skills.

4. **Bridging the critical and creative** We learned that combining critical thinking with creative practice bridges gaps between abstract concepts and students' everyday experiences. This made difficult subjects more relatable but also revealed how hard it can be for students to reflect on their own actions versus judging others.

At Don Bosco, the lab had a notable impact on both students and teachers. For the students, all girls in their third year of VMBO, the creative, hands-on activities provided an accessible and meaningful way to engage with the complex topic of disinformation. Many felt proud of their creations, especially the redesigned games and filter bubble mood boards, which helped them connect personal experiences with broader societal issues. The lab strengthened their critical thinking, made them more aware of how disinformation limits choice and fairness, and generated reflection on their role in promoting truth and justice.

For educators, the lab demonstrated the value of maker-based learning in fostering engagement and reflection among students who might struggle with abstract discussions. Teachers noted how these methods helped students internalise difficult concepts and felt that the project complemented social studies education well. The experience laid the groundwork for continued collaboration on media literacy and democracy.

The lab at Damstede Lyceum had a significant impact on both students and educators. For students, the hands-on game design process deepened their understanding of disinformation and its consequences for democracy. Many reported that creating something for a younger audience made them feel responsible and empowered. They developed greater awareness of how disinformation can create injustice, chaos, and mistrust in society. The collaborative work also strengthened critical thinking and communication skills, as students navigated differing ideas and perspectives.

Educators observed how creative, practical methods helped connect abstract concepts to students' lived experiences. The lab inspired new ways to integrate maker education and democratic reflection into existing curricula. While the direct community impact was limited during the lab itself, the students' intention to educate younger peers and their increased willingness to speak out suggest a

ripple effect that could support media literacy and democratic values beyond the classroom.

3.8.4 Waag Futurelab’s Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between Waag’s CCLABs.

Table 26 - Waag Futurelab's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	33
Participants from underrepresented groups	33
Educators	6
Other stakeholders	2
Researchers-facilitators	3
Number of participants (in final focus group)	6
Number of educators (in final interview)	3
Number of CSOs	0
Number of formal education organizations	5
Number of non-formal education organizations	2

3.9 University of Barcelona (Spain)

The University of Barcelona (UB) completed two labs during PAR Cycle 3 - one titled Pineda and two with TrinitatNova.

3.9.1 - Pineda

Geographical location	Pineda de Mar, Barcelona, Spain
Demographic characteristics of participants	16 students (16-17 years old, 3 female, 13 male)
Number of participants	16 students + 1 teacher + 1 educator-in-training
Number of sessions	6
Topic	Democracy and digital technologies

This CCLAB unfolded in the context of an elective course on Citizenship, Politics, and Law with 16 students aged 16–17. The lab set out to explore the relationship between digital technologies and democracy. The topic had been pre-selected by the teacher, which created some initial distance for students who struggled to find personal relevance with it.

The journey began with an individual reflective activity mapping their life stories with technology. Students created visual timelines, tracing their digital experiences from early childhood to the present. This opened a space for sharing, where concerns around addiction, distraction, harmful content (such as gore and pornography), and data privacy surfaced. One student’s declaration - "democracy is a failure" - sparked a vivid, unplanned discussion, revealing how cynically the group perceived the concept.

Figure 42 - A student's life story with technology

In the second session, students worked in small groups to define their research questions. However, disruptions – such as the teacher's absence and a late start – led to resistance and scattered attention. Despite this, students identified different topics: emotional impacts of TikTok, the addictive nature of social media, and suspicion toward apps that “steal data.” Discussions stayed mostly on the level of personal experience, with limited connections to broader political or structural issues.

Figure 43 - Mapping concerns about digital technology

Session three aimed to bridge this gap by asking them to trace the relation between digital technologies and democracy. Students initially equated democracy with voting or institutional politics and found it hard to link this with their research themes. But through dialogue, some began to recognise how algorithms and content moderation shape public opinion and participation. After this session, each group was asked to conduct initial research on the topic they selected, which were presented in session 4.

Presentations in session four showed a wide range of engagement. One group conducted a survey on phone addiction; another, made up of diverse female students that formed a tight group within an otherwise homogenous white male class, developed a debate game; while others showed little progress or resisted participation. Levels of engagement ranged from deeply critical to completely detached.

By session five, the girls' group stood out with a bold proposal: a gamified role-play on tech, politics, and intersectionality, alongside ideas for a civic hackathon and extracurricular debate club. Other groups experimented with speculative futures or shifted topics, often with mixed results.

The cycle closed with a focus group. Students expressed frustration over time constraints of the project. A key takeaway emerged: while some – particularly the girls – saw value in critical thinking and collective agency, many felt disempowered and sceptical about real democratic change within or beyond the school context.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 27 – Methods used during the Pineda lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding	Life Trajectory: My Experiences with Digital Technology	Participants created personal timelines illustrating their relationship with digital technologies and shared reflections on key moments and concerns.
Question	Brainstorming on Research Questions	In small groups, students selected specific themes and collaboratively developed research questions for their projects, followed by class-wide discussion.
Analyse	Brainstorming	Groups discussed three questions related to their topic, shared insights in a class discussion, and created a paper cartography to visualize connections.
Envision & Act (2 sessions)	Presenting Mini Research	Each group presented their mini research findings to the class and received facilitator feedback for refinement and further development.
Reflect	Final Focus Group	A concluding focus group gathered students' perceptions and reflections on the project, highlighting challenges, tensions, and transformative insights.

3.9.2 TrinitatNova

Geographical location	Trinitat Nova, a working-class neighbourhood in Barcelona's Nou Barris district, is home to a diverse migrant population. Despite longstanding social and economic challenges, the area is known for its strong
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	community spirit and activism, which have driven improvements in local infrastructure and public services since its development in the 1950s.
Demographic characteristics of participants	The school is classified as maximum complexity, with 70% of families in vulnerable socioeconomic situations. It serves a highly diverse student body, including many from migrant backgrounds-Asia, Latin America, Maghreb, Sub-Saharan Africa-and a significant Roma population.
Number of participants	Group T: 20 students (10 female and 10 male) Group N: 20 students (12 female and 8 male)
Number of sessions	5 on each group, 10 sessions in total.
Topic	Injustice in the school context.

This iteration of the CCLAB was planned in collaboration with a history teacher to conclude the subject’s curriculum with a unit on democracy and the modern world. Two iterations of this lap took place with differing groups (Group T and Group N) of students. The lab aligned well with the teacher’s decision to expand the curriculum by including content not officially covered – specifically Franco’s dictatorship and the Spanish democratic transition. The lab offered a hands-on, reflective approach to democratic values and practices in everyday life. For this version, technological aspects were intentionally set aside to focus on students’ capacity to express and internalize democratic ideals.

The first session began with a *Walking Debate* activity, where students responded to statements about youth agency and democratic participation. Initial prompts were light and engaging, gradually shifting toward more serious issues. The session concluded with students writing on sticky notes about injustices they had witnessed or experienced inside or outside the school.

In the second session, students were divided into three working groups. They categorized the injustices from the previous session into broader themes and selected the one they found most compelling. Then, using the metaphor of a “healthy cell” being infected by a “virus of injustice,” students designed cell structures to represent and analyse social injustices through creative, metaphorical thinking.

The third session continued this exploration by asking students to design the most socially unjust school possible. This satirical exercise prompted animated discussions, as students drew from real experiences of discrimination, lack of voice, excessive rules, and inadequate support. These shared stories provided emotional depth and fuelled their imaginative critique of authoritarian and dehumanizing aspects of education.

Figure 44 - Design output of 'imagining the most unjust school'

In the fourth session, students engaged in a role-playing activity. Drawing from the inequities identified in their fictional schools, they developed storyboards and performed short scenes depicting imagined, but relatable, unjust situations. This collective activity became a powerful outlet for expressing frustration and showcased the students' keen awareness of power dynamics within educational institutions.

Figure 45 - Forum theatre style role play with students

The final session brought all the threads together, focusing on the power of collective action. By drawing on students' prior experiences of collective protest within the school context, it was possible to trace a thread connecting their capacity for self-coordination and collective expression of concerns with the power and agency required to enact forms of everyday democracy in their immediate environment. The lab not only fostered critical thinking about democracy but also validated students' voices as active agents in their own educational experiences.

The below chart details the types of activities and methods employed during the sessions of the CCLAB, indicating how they align with the phases of the Critical ChangeLab Process.

Table 28 - Methods used during the TrinitatNova lab

Phase	Activity or Method	Description
Onboarding	Walking Debate	Participants physically positioned themselves along an agree-disagree spectrum in response to

		statements about youth agency and democracy, sparking discussion and reflection.
Question	The injustice Urn	Students anonymously wrote down personal experiences of unfairness, which were collected for future group reflection and analysis.
Analyse	Mapping Injustices through the Structure of a Cell	Groups used the metaphor of a biological cell to represent systemic injustices, translating experiences into visual 'organelles' within a shared diagram.
Envision	Designing the Most Socially Unjust Institute	Groups imagined and drew a fictional school embodying extreme injustice, exaggerating rules and dynamics to critically explore power and exclusion.
Envision & Act	Conflict Storyboard	Participants created illustrated storyboards depicting conflicts arising from systemic inequities in schools, setting the stage for later role-playing exercises.
Act	Role Playing (Theatre of the Oppressed style)	Students performed scenes of oppression and invited peers to intervene as protagonists, exploring realistic strategies for overcoming systemic injustice.
Reflect	Role Playing (TO style): Scene analysis (continued activity)	Participants revisited previously performed scenes to brainstorm and test alternative, nonviolent strategies for resolving conflicts and challenging power structures.

3.9.4 Key Learnings & Impact

Four key learnings emerged across the University of Barcelona's CCLABs. These include:

1. **Co-designing research topics fosters stronger engagement** Both labs showed that students connect more deeply when they help shape the questions for the study. In Pineda, the pre-selected topic limited some students' motivation; in Trinitat Nova, grounding inquiry in students' own experiences encouraged ownership and richer critical reflection.
2. **Creative and participatory methods enable inclusion** Activities such as visual life maps, small-group work, and arts-based approaches helped overcome entrenched participation dynamics. These methods created space

for quieter or marginalised students, especially girls of color, to share perspectives and subvert dominant discussion patterns.

3. **Adolescents' sense of injustice can drive civic engagement** Across both contexts students responded strongly to perceived unfairness. When recognised and supported, these reactions became a catalyst for critical thinking, democratic awareness, and in some cases, concrete civic initiatives like debate clubs and hackathons.
4. **Structural change in schools requires sustained integration** While the labs fostered meaningful moments of inclusion and agency, institutional constraints, gender imbalances, and entrenched power dynamics persisted. Educators stressed that lasting change depends on embedding participatory practices within broader school governance and culture.

The two labs fostered students' capacity to question, articulate, and act upon issues of relevance to their lives. Participants developed stronger critical thinking skills, greater awareness of structural inequalities, and a clearer understanding of democratic participation. In some cases, this translated into concrete initiatives, from proposals for hackathons and political debate clubs to community-oriented projects, demonstrating emerging youth agency. For marginalised groups, the labs provided platforms to challenge prevailing participation patterns and make their voices heard.

For educators, the process highlighted both the potential and the tensions of integrating participatory pedagogy into formal education. Teachers and facilitators gained insights into inclusive facilitation, creative engagement strategies, and the importance of balancing curriculum demands with student-led exploration. While the immediate institutional impact was modest and the broader community effects limited in the short term, the labs' longer-term potential lies in the skills, attitudes, and civic dispositions that students will carry into future contexts. By fostering critical consciousness, creativity, and collective agency, the labs have laid groundwork for continued democratic engagement beyond the school setting.

3.9.5 University of Barcelona's Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively between University of Barcelona's CCLABs.

Table 29 - University of Barcelona's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	59
Participants from underrepresented groups	50
Educators	4
Other stakeholders	0
Researchers-facilitators	6
Number of participants (in final focus group)	50
Number of educators (in final interview)	2
Number of CSOs	0
Number of formal education organizations	2
Number of non-formal education organizations	0

3.10 Tactical Tech (Germany, Labs in multiple countries)

Tactical Tech's report follows a different structure as, instead of conducting a Critical ChangeLab themselves, they coordinated eight labs with external partners from seven countries. As such, this chapter reflects how partners were onboarded, describes each external lab, and provides cumulative KPIs for the external labs.

Tactical Tech's onboarding process for external partners was developed to ensure clarity, consistency, and local relevance in planning and implementing Critical ChangeLabs within each partner's context. The process guided partners through the pedagogical framework, partnership expectations, workshop structures, and reporting requirements, while leaving space for adaptation and creativity.

Introduction and Orientation

The process began with an onboarding session for all external partners, introducing them to the Critical ChangeLab model. Tactical Tech presented the phases of the labs, thematic focus, and expectations regarding topics, methods, and local adaptation. Partners were also introduced to project values, including collaboration, inclusivity, and safeguarding. Following this, thematic "open houses" were offered, where partners could explore the framework in depth and receive tailored support.

Partnership Formalisation

To formalise the collaboration, partners submitted key documents before and after implementation. Pre-project submissions included:

- Session timetable – detailing planned activities, locations, and participant numbers
- Code of Conduct – read and signed to ensure alignment with Tactical Tech's ethical and operational standards
- Workshop structures – drawn from Tactical Tech's detailed outlines for Sessions 1–3, which partners could adapt for their local context

Post-project, partners submitted:

- Final report – detailing implementation, participant engagement, and outcomes
- Supporting documentation – such as self-assessment results, photographs of workshop outputs, and observations on participant learning

Delivery Requirements

Each partner aimed to implement three sessions with a group of 25–30 young participants aged 11–18 (ideally closer in age). While Tactical Tech provided structured workshop outlines, including session objectives, activities, facilitator tips, and materials, partners were encouraged to adapt formats, timings, and methods to best suit their community. For instance:

- Session 1 explored “participation in democracy” and “influence,” introducing concepts like algorithmic impact and online/offline engagement
- Session 2 focused on identifying topics participants cared about, clustering them, and refining problem statements
- Session 3 supported participants in creating advocacy outputs (e.g., posters, campaigns, videos) and reflecting on the process

Resources and Support

Tactical Tech equipped partners with:

- Pedagogical resources – recorded videos and written guides covering privacy, risk assessment, safeguarding, and impact measurement
- Communication and branding materials – logos, templates, social media guidelines, and recommendations for tracking and reporting impact
- Facilitation tools – detailed session outlines, activity cards, posters, and creative prompts to support interactive learning
- Ongoing Support and Reflection

Each partner had a dedicated Tactical Tech contact, with additional support available via project-specific email channels. Throughout the cycle, Tactical Tech upheld its commitment to data privacy, encouraging partners to familiarise themselves with the Data Use Policy.

At the end of PAR Cycle 2, a debrief brought all partners together to share local outcomes, reflect on methodology, and discuss changes in participants’ perspectives, behaviours, and attitudes. This reflective practice continued in Cycle 3, with facilitators capturing key learning moments, divergences, and commonalities for collective insight; this session is scheduled for after the summer holiday to accommodate external partners.

External Partner Onboarding

3.10.1 External Partner Labs

In this PAR Cycle, eight external partner labs focused on the topic of Influence, Participation, and Technology. The chart below details each lab, followed by a brief overview of how each lab engaged with and adjust the topic based on student input.

Table 30 - Overview of Tactical Tech's external labs

Partner	Location	Type of Institution	Number of Youth	Participant Demographics
Dedal Art School	Varna, Bulgaria	Non-formal educational centre (arts-focused)	11	Participants were between 11-30, with the majority being current or former students of the art school. Through our social media campaign and posters across the city, we further welcomed individuals who were not affiliated with the school.
Liceul Teoretic de Informatică „Grigore Moisil”	Iași, Romania	Public high school (mathematics and informatics focus)	26	School group formed by 6 girls, 21 boys, aged 15 - 17; studying maths and informatics
Center for Teacher Education, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade	Belgrade, Serbia	Formal higher education institution (teacher training)	12	The group consisted of two boys and ten girls aged 16-18. Four students attend the school for shipping shipbuilding and hydro-engineering, while the other eight students attend grammar schools.
Dijital Esenlik at Hisar Schools	Istanbul, Turkey	Formal K-12 educational institution	25	13 years old (7th-grade) private school students

Televele Media Education Association at Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium	Budapest, Hungary	Secondary grammar school	33	The participants were 14-year-old students from class 8.B at the Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium. The school is located in Budapest and functions as a six-grade secondary grammar school. The students primarily reside in the capital or its metropolitan area and mostly come from financially stable and supportive family environments. Academically, the school is considered average in the Hungarian context.
FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium (Lab 1)	Berlin, Germany	Secondary school	24	This lab was held at a humanities-oriented high school in Berlin with a group of 9 th graders. Students from this class just happen to be having classes together, therefore did not consider themselves one community and reported not feeling heard.
FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium (Lab 2)	Berlin, Germany	Secondary school	25	This lab was held with a group of 9th graders from a humanities-centred high school in Berlin over two sessions. This lab, contrary to the other one at this high school, took place partially outside of school premisses.
Criar Cidade at Associação de Moradores do Bairro Horizonte	Portugal	Non-formal: after school club	13	This lab involved 12-18 years old, from social housing neighbourhoods and/or migrant families, many of them come from a racialised background.

Dedal Art School for Children from Disadvantaged Background (Bulgaria)

The lab in Varna, Bulgaria, was hosted by Dedal Art School, a non-formal educational space providing free classes in fine, contemporary and digital arts for children and young people from disadvantaged backgrounds. Over four sessions, participants aged 11 to 30 engaged in discussions on democracy, civic participation, and media literacy, with a strong focus on recognizing and resisting propaganda and misinformation. Creative exercises and debates encouraged intergenerational dialogue and critical thinking, helping participants identify both community challenges and possible solutions. The lab inspired a sense of agency among attendees, many of whom expressed a desire to share what they learned and called for more initiatives like this in Bulgaria's challenging socio-political context.

Liceul Teoretic de Informatică „Grigore Moisil Iași (Romania)

The lab in Iași, Romania, took place at Liceul Teoretic de Informatică „Grigore Moisil, a public high school specializing in mathematics and informatics. Across three sessions, 26 students aged 15–17 explored how participation, influence, and technology intersect in shaping democratic engagement. Activities included debates, problem-mapping, and advocacy planning, leading students to propose creative responses to local issues such as deforestation, educational pressures, and traffic congestion. Outputs ranged from posters and poems to ideas for social media campaigns. Stakeholders praised the students' maturity and insight, and the school expressed interest in extending this pedagogical approach to other classes.

Figure 46 - Participants group work CCLAB at Colegiul Moisil (Romania)

Center for Teacher Education (Serbia)

The lab in Belgrade, Serbia, was hosted by the Center for Teacher Education at the Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, a formal education institution that trains future educators. Over three sessions, participants aged 16–18 explored influence, youth participation, and ways to foster change in their communities, all within the context of ongoing student and civil protests in Serbia. Activities included interactive discussions, spectrogram debates, and collaborative visual campaigns on topics such as youth activism, stereotypes, and civic engagement. Despite challenges in participant recruitment due to school disruptions from protests and strikes, the lab created space for meaningful reflection and collaboration. Students reported increased confidence in their ability to make issues visible and take action, while stakeholders expressed interest in adapting the activities to their own educational and community contexts.

Dijital Esenlik (Turkey)

The lab in Istanbul, Turkey, was hosted by Dijital Esenlik at Hisar Schools, a formal K–12 educational institution. Conducted over two days with 25 seventh-grade students, the lab explored influence, democracy, and youth participation, blending personal experiences from digital life with reflections on broader social issues. Activities such as spectrogram debates, clustering exercises, and advocacy planning led students to address topics ranging from gender equality and environmental pollution to sports fanaticism and the value of art education.

Participants developed creative advocacy outputs, including posters, T-shirt designs, and manifestos, and showed measurable growth in their ability to imagine solutions and use creative resources for social impact. While some expressed limited optimism about change in their national context, the process strengthened their skills and confidence, prompting the school to consider expanding the program to more classes.

Figure 47 – Youth output from Turkey

Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium (Hungary)

The lab in Budapest, Hungary, was hosted by Televele Media Education Association at Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium, a six-grade secondary grammar school. Over two sessions, 14-year-old students explored the concept of influence and identified social issues they felt strongly about, ranging from education reform and healthcare quality to environmental protection and digital rights. Through brainstorming, spectrogram debates, and advocacy project development, ten student teams created practical and creative campaign proposals, including mock apps, awareness campaigns, and community initiatives. The process encouraged open dialogue, linked personal experiences with systemic issues, and strengthened students' critical thinking, collaboration, and confidence in expressing opinions.

Observers praised the depth, empathy, and originality of the students' work, with several ideas showing potential for real-world implementation.

Szexuális felvilágosítás hiánya

- Alapos felvilágosítás a kornak megfelelően
- Szakemberekkel alaposság
- Lelki támogatás
- Filmek ---- könnyebben eljut az emberekhez
- Társadalmilag nem tabuként kezelni

Figure 48 – Poster from Bethlen Gábor Általános Iskola és Gimnázium (credit: Televele, Hungary)

FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium – Lab 1 (Germany)

Two labs were hosted in Berlin, Germany by Sartre Gymnasium, a secondary school, and engaged 24 ninth-grade students over three sessions. The lab explored democracy, influence, and activism, beginning with discussions on democratic participation, sources of influence, and the role of algorithms in shaping online experiences. Through activities such as spectrogram debates, a world café on local and global issues, and group campaign development, students identified concerns including political extremism, sexualised public advertising, the school system, and political competence. While class divisions and reluctance to collaborate across social groups posed challenges, several teams produced campaign ideas – from reducing sexualized advertising to introducing elective subjects from ninth grade. By the end, participants reported greater understanding of how to organise campaigns and recognized practical tools for civic engagement, though some expressed uncertainty about the broader purpose of the workshops.

FEZ Berlin at Sartre Gymnasium – Lab 2 (Germany)

The second lab hosted by Sartre Gymnasium involved 25 ninth-grade students over two days. Held partly at FEZ Berlin and partly at the school, the lab explored democracy, participation, and campaigning, beginning with defining key concepts and mapping sources of influence. Students identified concerns ranging from political issues – such as police violence, racism in social media, and discrimination in housing – to local challenges like drug use in public spaces and high cafeteria prices. Working in groups, they developed campaign ideas including educational initiatives, awareness efforts, and practical solutions like a student-run sandwich system to reduce lunch costs. While some groups struggled to define their audiences or refine their goals, the process encouraged research, critical discussion, and collaboration, with several students reporting increased confidence in their ability to contribute to change.

Criar Cidade at Associação Moradores do Bairro Horizonte (Portugal)

This lab was conducted by Criar Cidade in collaboration with the coordinator of the AMBH association’s educational programme. The lab involved 13 participants, ages 12–18 years old, from social housing neighbourhoods and/or migrant families, many from a marginalized background. They all regularly participate in the AMBH association’s afternoon activities. Teens welcomed the possibility to speak up and collaborate since the group often felt they were not listened and had little opportunities to express their opinions and contribute with ideas. Participants decided to focus on two problem statements: 1. the harassment teenage girls suffer and 2. the conditions of their school. This last topic was divided in two key sub-topics: a. the conditions of the school infrastructure and materials, b. How the adult staff, especially teachers, treat students.

3.10.2 Key Learnings & Impact

While each external partner had specific key takeaways related to their local context, there were shared learnings across the partners. These shared learnings include:

1. **The relevance of addressing the intersection of online influence and democratic youth participation** Local partners reported that participants

found the topic interesting, particularly in countries where currently there are democratic processes highly influenced by digital technologies and social media platforms like Romania, Serbia and Turkey.

2. **CCLAB bottom-up approach as very effective to raise critical thinking and increase youth agency to engage in everyday democracy** Most partners reported an increase in awareness and agency of participants.
3. **Flexibility and trust in host organisations are key to overcoming barriers in lab implementation** In contexts where young people already presented mistrust in democratic processes and institutions, the implementation of the lab was particularly challenging demanding more flexibility, negotiation and conflict management skills by the facilitators. A better profiling of the group ahead of the lab and more time in phases 1 and 2 were also recommendations given by educators.

3.10.3 Tactical Tech Key Performance Indicators

The table below reflects the number of people engaged cumulatively by the external labs coordinated by Tactical Tech.

Table 31 - Tactical Tech's KPIs

Participants in PAR cycle	169
Participants from underrepresented groups	59
Educators	36
Other stakeholders	3
Researchers-facilitators	19
Number of participants (in final focus group)	0
Number of educators (in final interview)	0
Number of CSOs	6
Number of formal education organizations	6
Number of non-formal education organizations	5

4. Twinning Programme

During PAR Cycle 3, a twinning programme was set up. During these twinships, two Critical ChangeLab partners paired together to engage youth in international collaboration. The aim was for young people to exchange ideas relating to the project and their lab with peers from another country; this exchange could be completed synchronously or asynchronously. This chapter documents each twinship including their activities, output, and key learnings.

Overall, the twinning process improved youth participants active engagement with the project. It provided a clearer sense of purpose and made their work feel more relevant to their own lives and within a broader global context. Many participants expressed excitement and fascination at the opportunity for international collaboration, where comparing and contrasting the different approaches cultivated a strong sense of connection.

4.1 Trinity College Dublin & Ars Electronica

Geographical location	Dublin & Perg, Upper-Austria
Demographic characteristics of participants	<p>Dublin Youth, aged 15-16. 12 F, 7M</p> <p>Perg 14 female, 2 male participants Aged 16-18</p>

As both of the labs (TCD & AE) were focused on imagining futures, the twinship focused on that aspect of our programmes. The twinship consisted of one main activity, which was Postcards from the Future.

Figure 49 – Postcards from the Future, Dublin

After imagining the future of Dublin, participants were then encouraged to imagine how they specifically contributed to creating that future. They wrote and drew postcards that depicted their images of the future and their places in it, creating ‘postcards from the future’. The TCD postcards were posted to Ars Electronica, for their participants to reflect on. In turn, the Ars Electronica participants created their own postcards from the future which participants in TCD reflected on a few months later as part of a follow-up programme.

Figure 50 - Postcards from the Future

The outputs were postcards from the future from both the Irish and Austrian participants. These postcards captured the participants' imaginings of the future and identified the roles they played to bring that future into being.

Lessons Learned

The participants were excited by the exchange. Even though it was quite simple, and people their age can connect with people across the world through the internet, the materiality of creating something physical and creative to physically be sent to other people excited them and added an element of pride to their postcards.

When Irish students received postcards from Austria they were very engaged and compared the futures that Austrian participants wanted to see to their own visions. Again, the physicality of the postcards was a big appeal, and participants enjoyed thinking about the people who had created these visions and their motivations.

They felt a sense of connection to the other participants through comparing and contrasting their visions. The facilitator from TCD showed students visions of the future from the past before (An l'Ean 2000) but their engagement with these postcards was different - definitely a better sense of connection.

Whereas the Austrian participants were very interested in seeing the Irish postcards as well, they did need a bit more prompting to engage with them - as this group struggled a lot with issues like confidence and self-worth. The thought of comparing their ideas about the future with others seemed to many of them a bit intimidating. But eventually they overcame their initial reluctance, very much motivated as well by the thought of sending the physical postcards to Dublin.

4.2 Institute for Social Research & Kersnikova

Geographical location	Zagreb, Croatia and Ljubljana, Slovenia
Demographic characteristics of participants	<p>Zagreb</p> <p>Participants were students living in a female student dorm "Učenički dom Marije Jambrišak", thus all the participants were women, 13 in total. Participants were high school students, aged 15 to 18 years old, with most of them being 15 and 16 years old. The participants were fluent in English language which was chosen as a Twinning language.</p> <p>Ljubljana</p> <p>Participants were children (11-15) that frequent the Skupna Točka community center. There were 26 participants in total, about 2/3 were boys. Participants were fluent in English which was chosen as a Twinning language.</p>

At the end of each partner’s lab session, a smaller group of students came together to reflect on the activities and discussions. They exchanged thoughts on what they found most interesting or thought-provoking, identified key moments, and collaboratively wrote a short summary capturing the essence of the session. This process reinforced learning and encouraged teamwork, critical reflection, and communication skills.

These written session summaries were shared with their twinning partner group, who analysed and discussed the differences and similarities in their experiences and interpretations. Based on this comparative reflection, participants had an option to ask questions about partners’ activities if additional elaboration was needed.

Participants found it particularly fascinating to observe how different their twinning partner’s approach was compared to their own, even though both groups were working toward similar goals. This contrast offered valuable insight into how shared objectives can be pursued through completely different paths. It helped broaden participants’ understanding of the diversity in problem-solving and project planning, emphasizing that there is not a single “correct” method.

Moreover, participants realised that a group’s approach is often shaped by its specific context – available knowledge, experience, and resources. This encouraged them to reflect more critically on their own methods, becoming more open to alternative perspectives. The activity helped them recognise the importance of flexibility, empathy, and dialogue when working in democratic and diverse setting.

The main output of the Twinning activity was a collaboratively created Miro Board, which featured detailed descriptions of the activities conducted by both partner groups. Given that both groups chose the asynchronous format – largely due to scheduling conflicts and numerous school responsibilities – the Miro Board emerged as the most practical and effective solution for collaboration and exchange. It allowed participants to share their experiences visually and interactively, fostering mutual understanding without the constraints of real-time communication. Moreover, the Miro Board served as a dynamic tool for tracking progress throughout the sessions, offering a visual timeline of engagement.

Figure 51 – A screenshot of the Miro Board of Twinning activities

It also functioned as a reflective space where participants could learn about each other’s approaches, ideas, and key takeaways. This Miro Board can also serve as a valuable learning resource for future PAR cycle participants, offering them a clear

and engaging visual overview of the session flow from start to finish. By exploring the documented activities, reflections, and outcomes, new participants can gain deeper insight into the structure, progression, and key components of the PAR cycle. It not only helps them understand what to expect but also inspires ideas for their own participation and encourages critical engagement with the process.

Lessons Learned

Exposure to different approaches used by other groups is highly beneficial for participants' engagement in the PAR cycle. It encourages them to think more creatively and adopt an "out-of-the-box" mindset. By observing how others tackle similar issues using diverse strategies, participants come to understand that complex social phenomena rarely have a single "right" solution. Instead, the same problem can be approached in multiple valid ways, depending on context, resources, and perspective. This awareness fosters flexibility, critical thinking, and a deeper appreciation for diversity in problem-solving within collaborative learning environments.

4.3 University of Oulu & University of Barcelona

Geographical location	Oulu, Finland and Barcelona, Spain
Demographic characteristics of participants	<p>Oulu 15–17-year-old 20 participants (11 Girls, 9 Boys) 6 girls and 3 boys from immigrant background</p> <p>Barcelona 16–17-year-old 16 participants (4 Girls, 12 Boys) 4 girls from immigrant background</p>

The twinning between UOULU and UB developed differently from other twinships. Due to logistical constraints, it was difficult to achieve direct collaboration between students; instead, the two partners worked to iteratively develop ideas. UB shared an initial draft of their activity design with UOULU, offering a foundational framework for UOULU’s lab development. While both labs explored the broader theme of digital technologies, UB’s approach maintained a general focus, whereas UOULU adapted the concept to specifically investigate artificial intelligence in decision-making. The twinning programme consisted of two key activities:

Activity 1: Exploring the Relationship Between Democracy and Digital Technologies

UB’s activity encouraged students to explore the relationship between democracy and digital technologies through collective mapping and discussion, serving as a catalyst for participatory inquiry. At UB, the activity began with participants creating a visual timeline to chart the evolution of their relationship with digital technologies from childhood to the present. This initial exercise served as a catalyst, prompting a discussion on various concerns regarding the impact of mobile technologies on their daily lives. These concerns were then mapped onto a large sheet of craft paper at the center of the room.

Following this mapping exercise, group reflection followed to find the interconnections between the identified themes, specifically addressing technology addiction, exposure to gore content, data privacy breaches, and its implications for democratic processes. Grounded in this discussion, each group

was tasked with refining a specific research question and proposing a methodology for further investigation.

Building on this, and benefiting from the different implementation timelines, UOULU extended and contextualised the activity to align with their thematic priorities, enabling a more targeted exploration of AI's societal implications. The participants in the UOULU lab started by drawing what democracy might look like in practice. From this first drawing, the participants were asked to reconsider this democracy in the situation where AI makes decisions and draw a picture of a new version of democracy. These two drawings became the starting point for reflection on finding connections between democracy and AI. Participants wrote their thoughts on sticky notes and drew lines to connect two circles representing Democracy and AI in decision making.

Figure 52 - Participants are reflecting on connections between Democracy and AI in decision making

Activity 2: Looking for plausible, possible and desirable futures

The second activity shared by UB involved students imagining two contrasting future scenarios; one representing the best possible outcome and the other the worst related to digital technology addiction. In UB, this activity employed speculative fiction to disrupt conventional thinking, tasking participants with envisioning extreme technological futures. The pedagogical aim was to stimulate critical analysis of tech dependency through the articulation of its potential consequences.

UOULU built on this concept by expanding the scope to explore possible, plausible, and desirable futures in the context of AI and decision-making. This adaptation was facilitated through the use of a futures triangle template, allowing students to critically engage with multiple trajectories and drivers of technological change.

Figure 53 - Participants sharing insights from their future triangles

In the UOULU lab, participants worked in small groups to reflect on the issue under discussion (AI in decision making) from different temporalities. They looked at the present issue and researched what past actions led to these present challenges. From there, they moved to envision the futures that seem plausible and the futures that are desirable. Their reflection moved back and forth from future to present and what do they need to change today to have the desired futures. At the end each presented their future triangle which was followed by questions and discussion.

As outputs of the twinship, participants several visual outputs including timelines, drawings, connection maps, and a Miro board. The timelines documented the evolution of each participant's relationship with digital technologies. It allowed rich debate and the definition of key themes to focus the participatory research process. Drawings reflected on democracy and later drew again to show how this vision of Democracy changes if AI is responsible for making decisions. Participants also made connection maps (paper template filled with sticky notes and lines connecting the two circles representing democracy and AI in decision making). Finally, they made a Miro board with future triangles.

Lessons Learned

Although the labs did not collaborate directly or run concurrently, the twinning approach enabled mutual inspiration and iterative development of ideas. The twinning happened in the context of using similar/same methods to involve the participants. UOULU built on the activities used by UB in their lab. As the two twinning labs took place at different times, there was no exchange of information or insights between the participants from the two labs. This shows the difficulty of planning this type of twinning and shows the importance of logistical constraints in this type of endeavour.

Considering the time constraints, both in terms of the limited number of sessions that could be carried out and the need to align with the specific calendars of each hosting institution, designing a Twinning program that could be meaningful proved to be a challenge. At the same time, language differences posed an additional difficulty, since we considered that, at least in the Spanish context, students would not feel comfortable and would not participate in the same way if English were the vehicular language. Furthermore, additional issues arise in terms of planning a twinning program when we consider the specificity of each context and topic selection. In this regard, our reflection is that, to implement a Twinning program within a participatory action research cycle, it is necessary to work with a different temporality (e.g., long-term processes).

4.4 Waag Futurelab & Tactical Tech

Geographical location	Romania and the Netherlands
Demographic characteristics of participants	<p>Romania: School group formed by 6 girls, 21 boys, aged 15 – 17. Studying primarily Maths and Informatics; have been exposed to different activities related to media literacy, democracy, EU values etc.</p> <p>Netherlands: Pre-vocational secondary education students. Group of girls, aged 15+</p>

Given the language barriers and the different schedules of the participating partners, we chose to implement an asynchronous twinning program between two Critical Change Labs: one in Romania and one in the Netherlands. The goals of this exchange were threefold. First, it aimed to give participants the opportunity to learn about the discussions and outputs from a Critical ChangeLab implemented in another European country with teenagers. Second, it provided space for sharing and gaining insights from fellow teenagers on their work, encouraging reflection on the realities of young people in another context – insights that could help inform their own process. Third, it sought to foster dialogue and solidarity among teenagers across Europe.

The structure of the exchange was as follows. The Romanian students recorded a short video in which they shared with the Dutch participants the deliverables from their lab, as well as their experiences of taking part in the process. The Dutch students, in turn, recorded a video in which they shared their perspectives on everyday democracy and the impact that disinformation could have.

Both labs watched the videos and provided feedback on each other’s work, creating a space to exchange learnings and insights. This asynchronous exchange enabled two groups of young people, who otherwise would likely never have met, to share their experiences with peers from a different country. It offered them the opportunity to receive feedback from fellow Critical ChangeLab participants abroad, and to learn about the different ways that topics such as youth and everyday democracy were approached in another national and cultural context.

Figure 54 - Screenshot from student video on pressure of mandatory subjects

Guided conversations took place in each location, centred on the deliverables produced by the counterpart lab. Facilitators from both teams jointly prepared a set of guiding questions for discussions with participating teenagers. These conversations invited students to reflect on whether they recognised themselves in the work, which pieces resonated most, the intended message of each video, the clarity of that message, and how they might personally approach the issues presented. In Romania, students were also asked to complete a short feedback form.

In Romania, each team produced a tangible outcome: a poem, a poster, and three short videos designed as part of a potential social media campaign. The work generated further opportunities - during Session 3, an attending informatics teacher offered to help students develop an online platform providing practical guidance on school subjects. Students approached the issues with notable seriousness, creating ideas that could feasibly become student-led projects. With sustained guidance and follow-up sessions, these concepts could evolve into concrete initiatives with real impact in their communities.

Figure 55 – Screenshot from student video that argues learnings should be about curiosity, not just tests

In the Netherlands, the CCLAB focused on the topic of disinformation, examining its different forms, its influence on everyday democracy, and possible strategies to reduce its harmful effects. Through discussion and reflection, participants developed a series of videos addressing these concerns, offering their own perspectives and suggested responses.

Lessons Learned

Participants really appreciated the opportunity to share their experiences with teens from another country, as they saw it as an opportunity for their reflections and outputs to have an impact beyond their own context. It provided an extra validation to the relevance of these types of interventions.

The exchange outputs, although coming from different countries and realities, resonated with participants, giving them a sense that they are not alone in their concerns and that they have something in common with each other.

4.5 LATRA & European Alternatives

Geographical location	Lesvos, Greece and Paris, France
Demographic characteristics of participants	<p>Greece 15 students</p> <p>Paris 18 students</p> <p>Students do not share a common language.</p>

Greek and French participants collaborated asynchronously to co-create storytelling zines. Each group intentionally left their zines unfinished, allowing their counterparts to continue and complete them. The French participants sent their zines to Lesvos, where the Greek participants added their contributions and finalized them. LATRA then personally delivered the finalized zines to Paris. The Greek participants' productions were then given again to the French participants to further complete. This creative exchange resulted in a collection of co-created zines that weave together diverse perspectives, narratives, and artistic styles. Key activities included zine creation, zine exchange, and zine completion, fostering a tangible connection and cultural exchange between the two groups.

Figure 56 – A collaborative zine created by Euroalter participants featuring diverse themes including environmental concerns (melting Earth), digital technology impacts (AI fears and dependence), and humanity’s relationship with technology. The zine showcases the visual storytelling approach used in the twinning exchange, combining collage, drawings, and text to communicate complex ideas across language barriers.

The output of the twinship is a collection of co-created storytelling zines that blend the artistic and narrative contributions of both Greek and French participants. The final zines have been digitized and will be shared online, showcasing the diverse perspectives and artistic styles that emerged from this collaborative exchange.

Figure 57 - A collaborative zine spread featuring data visualization themes with elements including "DATA OVER DIV," "ALGORITHMIC," "DEMOCRACY," and "RISK." The artwork combines digital aesthetics with analogue collage techniques, incorporating geometric patterns, data charts, and surveillance imagery (blue eye) to explore themes of data governance and digital democracy. This example demonstrates the cross-cultural artistic dialogue achieved through the twinning exchange between Greek and French participants.

Lessons Learned

One key lesson learned is the effectiveness of asynchronous collaboration in bridging geographical and linguistic divides. Despite not sharing a common language, participants successfully co-created zines by relying on visual communication and translation where necessary. This approach fostered a unique creative exchange, allowing diverse perspectives and artistic styles to merge. The physical exchange of zines also created a tangible connection between the groups, reinforcing the collaborative nature of the project and encouraging deep engagement with another culture's creative expression. The physicality of the zine allowed the students to engage strongly with the object. The French students

enjoyed seeing and reading the result of the “merged” inputs between the French and the Greek inputs.

The participants experienced the exchange through a creative and collaborative process, where they initiated and completed zines from their counterparts. This involved engaging with different artistic styles and narratives, fostering a sense of shared creation despite geographical distance. This exchange allowed participants to blend diverse perspectives and narratives. It encouraged them to employ visual vocabulary for communication and engage deeply with another culture’s creative expression, leading to a collection of co-created storytelling zines.

5. Key Learnings from PAR Cycle 3

Many learnings emerged during PAR Cycle 3; this section contains an overview of these learnings both related to the implementation of the PAR Cycle and the Twinning Programme. A full and detailed exploration and analysis of learnings from PAR Cycle 3 is provided in Deliverable 3.1.

PAR Cycle 3 Implementation

In PAR Cycle 3, the Question & Analyse phases emerged as a fluid and iterative process, where defining the theme, co-constructing knowledge, and broadening perspectives constantly overlapped. Theme definition ranged from educator-led framing to fully participant-defined topics, with co-shaped approaches in between. Predetermined themes provided coherence but could limit ownership; participant-defined themes fostered high engagement but sometimes required facilitation to ensure scope and relevance. In most cases, defining the theme proved to be an ongoing negotiation, revisited as the inquiry evolved.

Co-constructing knowledge was as much relational as analytical. Dialogic spaces invited participants to share experiences, exchange interpretations, and collectively make sense of the theme. Knowledge was built through diverse forms, like discussion, creative co-production, embodied activities, and playful exploration, while emotions were valued as legitimate insights. These practices deepened engagement but also posed challenges, including maintaining equitable participation, sustaining focus amid divergent perspectives, and working through conflict without closing off dialogue.

Broadening perspectives occurred throughout rather than after co-construction. Cooperative inquiry across settings, engagement with cultural events, and encounters with expert voices often unsettled assumptions and expanded socio-political awareness. Their impact depended on integration: external perspectives worked best when positioned as provocations rather than authoritative conclusions, ensuring they complemented rather than overshadowed participants' lived knowledge.

New perspectives often prompted groups to revisit their framing, while co-construction could revitalize a theme chosen with less initial participant input. The

strength of both the Question & Analyse phases lay in holding openness and structure in tension, valuing multiple ways of knowing, and enabling inquiry that was responsive to change.

If this first phase grounded inquiry, the Envision & Act phases brought it into dialogue with possible futures. Approaches varied: envisioning served as a way to surface hopes and fears, critically reflect on the present, unsettle dominant thinking, and/or lay groundwork for concrete proposals. These orientations reflected different epistemologies - future forecasting, grounded in extrapolation from present trends, and speculative futures, which used imagination to break from what is likely or known.

The value of envisioning lay in balancing creative openness with pathways toward action. When linked too tightly to immediate planning, imaginative exploration risked narrowing prematurely; when left entirely open-ended, participants could struggle to connect ideas to change. Effective facilitation created spaces for experimentation, contradiction, and refinement before moving forward. In some contexts, envisioning led directly to action design and implementation; in others, it generated seeds for future work beyond the cycle.

Together, the learnings from these phases showed that questioning and imagining are intertwined. Critical analysis shapes what can be envisioned, and envisioning reframes the questions themselves. When participants are given time, tools, and trust to move between grounded inquiry and expansive possibility, they can generate both a deeper understanding of the present and richer visions for the future.

Twinning Programme

The cross-cultural scope of the twinning process contributed to a sense of comfort and reassurance amongst youth, as participants realized that they were not alone in their concerns or discussions. The comparative element of the twin pairings broadened participants' perspectives and encouraged more creative, "outside the box" thinking. At the same time, one group found it slightly intimidating to compare their own ideas of the future with another group.

The process allowed them to reflect on their own problem-solving approaches in conjunction with those of their partners. This heightened their awareness of how cultural, linguistic, and geographical contexts shape approaches toward shared challenges. This activity also increased participants' recognition of the importance of flexibility, empathy, and dialogue when working in diverse settings. Most pairs reported a deeper appreciation for varied perspectives, recognizing that there is no single right answer or approach to these discussions.

Two twin pairs particularly emphasised the benefits of working with physical materials. The passing on of a tangible creation to their partner strengthened the sense of connection and cultural exchange. It also added elements of pride, passion and ownership to the process, and participants felt motivated by the idea that their work would be physically received by their peers. The LATRA and European Alternatives pair described the physical merging of the participants' artistic and narrative contributions in a zine as particularly impactful.

However, despite the value of physical materials, increased notions of connection and collaboration were also reported by twin pairs working exclusively online. One pair who collaborated on a shared Miro board found the tool very visually engaging and accessible. Another pair who exchanged videos also reported feelings of community and shared understanding.

Regardless of the collaborative material used, all pairs used asynchronous methods as a means of bridging geographical and linguistic divides with the exception of OULU and UB. This approach ensured that mutual inspiration could occur without practical limitations, allowing the use of visual methods and translations. Even the pair that collaborated less explicitly still found that the twinning approach contributed to idea development, inspiration and cross-cultural learning. Time constraints in the example of the Oulu & University of Barcelona, however, show the importance of temporality within the planning of a twinship.

Overall, the twinning process was impactful in encouraging thoughtful reflection and discussion on cultural contexts and varied perceptions. The process contributed to cross-cultural engagement, communication and understanding.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable has documented the third PAR cycle of Critical ChangeLabs, where young people and communities across Europe continued to explore what democracy means in their own lives. This PAR cycle demonstrated that the Critical ChangeLab model can adapt to diverse local realities while remaining rooted in the shared goal of strengthening democratic participation. By combining creative methods, collaborative inquiry, and context-specific approaches, partners succeeded in creating spaces where participants could connect abstract democratic ideas with the everyday challenges and opportunities they face.

The PAR cycle yielded clear evidence of impact. Young people not only engaged in structured activities but also shaped discussions and generated new ideas of their own. Many reported greater confidence in speaking publicly, collaborating with peers, and linking personal experiences to broader societal issues. The Community of Practice also played a central role, enabling partners to share strategies, reflect on challenges, and adapt the model in ways that deepened its effectiveness across settings.

At the same time, the process illuminated important limitations. Sustaining engagement proved difficult in some contexts, particularly when activities were embedded in formal education systems with limited flexibility. Questions of inclusivity and power dynamics also emerged: while many participants, especially young women, found empowerment through the labs, others felt their ability to influence real decision-making remained limited. This tension between the energy of youth participation and the structural barriers that constrain it is one of the most significant findings of the PAR cycle. It underscores the need to connect the imaginative work of the labs with clearer pathways to civic influence and longer-term change.

The lessons from this PAR cycle point to several priorities for the future. Creative and hands-on methods are consistently effective in supporting engagement, particularly when grounded in local issues that participants recognize as their own.

Facilitation must remain flexible, responsive, and attentive to group dynamics, ensuring that all voices are heard. And across contexts, there is value in continuing to treat the labs not as fixed programmes but as evolving practices that grow through reflection, adaptation, and exchange.

In the end, the third cycle of Critical ChangeLabs has shown that democracy can be learned, tested, and re-imagined in shared spaces of creativity and inquiry. These findings will inform the Critical ChangeLab Educator Handbook, which will serve as a guide for educators in practically implementing strategies tested during this project to increase youth agency in participation in democracy. While results of these labs are uneven, as is inevitable in participatory practice, they provide important evidence of both the possibilities and the limits of youth engagement today. Most importantly, they affirm that democratic culture is strengthened when young people are given the tools and the trust to explore it together, with all the complexity and contradiction that such exploration entails.

